

> DESIRE6G <

**D4.2 Interim report on the unified
programmable data plane layer of
DESIRE6G**

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Abstract

This document presents an interim report detailing the implementation and development of the unified data plane layer within the DESIRE6G architecture, as part of the work conducted in WP4 from months 12 to 23. Building upon the requirements and architecture defined in WP2, the report describes the initial prototypes of the different components, their preliminary evaluation results, current limitations, and plans for improvement. It covers enhancements to network service deployment, data plane techniques, programmable traffic management, monitoring solutions, and hardware accelerators. These components collectively address performance, latency, and resource-sharing challenges, enabling a cloud-native approach to packet processing. The document assumes familiarity with DESIRE6G terminology and architecture and complements earlier deliverables D2.2 and D4.1.

Keywords

Programmable data plane, local NFVO, VIM, cloud-native, network function, programmable traffic management, multi-tenancy, in-band telemetry, hardware acceleration

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	16
2	Architecture and components of the unified programmable data plane	18
3	Components for deployment and configuration of network service subgraphs.....	20
3.1	Enhanced VIM	20
3.1.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art	21
3.1.2	Implementation.....	21
3.1.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	22
3.1.4	Evaluation.....	22
3.1.5	Limitations and further plans.....	23
3.2	IML-Local Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator	24
3.2.1	Implementation.....	25
3.2.2	Evaluation.....	28
3.2.3	Limitations and further plans.....	29
4	Infrastructure network functions for network service execution	31
4.1	UE2ServiceMapper	31
4.1.1	Implementation.....	32
4.2	NF Routing	33
4.2.1	Implementation.....	33
4.2.2	Transport adapter functions.....	34
4.3	Integration into IML's Local NFVO.....	35
4.4	Limitations and further plans.....	35
5	Cloud-native data plane components	36
5.1	Run-time Load Optimizer	36

5.1.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art.....	37
5.1.2	Implementation.....	38
5.1.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	43
5.1.4	Evaluation.....	44
5.1.5	Limitations and further plans.....	46
5.2	IML-Control Plane Proxy.....	46
5.2.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art.....	47
5.2.2	Implementation.....	48
5.2.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	49
5.2.4	Evaluation.....	51
5.2.5	Limitations and further plans.....	51
5.3	P4 Data Plane Aggregator.....	51
5.3.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art.....	52
5.3.2	Implementation.....	53
5.3.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	55
5.3.4	Evaluation.....	55
5.3.5	Limitations and further plans.....	57
6	Performance isolation for supporting deep slicing.....	58
6.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art.....	59
6.2	Performance isolation within a slice.....	60
6.2.1	Implementation.....	62
6.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	64
6.4	Evaluation.....	66
6.4.1	PPV method with the scalable packet marker.....	66
6.5	Limitations and further plans.....	69

7	Components in the pervasive monitoring framework	70
7.1	MAS Telemetry agent	70
7.1.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art	70
7.1.2	Implementation	71
7.1.3	Usage and Interfaces	72
7.1.4	Evaluation	73
7.1.5	Limitations and further plans	74
7.2	Telemetry collector and in-network control	74
7.2.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art	74
7.2.2	Implementation	75
7.2.3	Usage and Interfaces	77
7.2.4	Evaluation	78
7.3	P4 In-band Network Telemetry on UE.....	80
7.3.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art	81
7.3.2	Implementation	81
7.3.3	Usage and Interfaces	86
7.3.4	Evaluation	86
7.4	RAN Telemetry Exposure	89
7.4.1	Novelty Beyond the State-of-the-Art	90
7.4.2	Implementation	92
7.4.3	Scalability and Future Enhancements	95
7.5	Software monitoring	95
7.5.1	Mapping with DESIRE-6G architecture	95
7.5.2	Principle	95
7.5.3	Novelty beyond the state of the art	96

7.5.4	First experiments, future work and Implementation.....	97
7.5.5	Limitations.....	99
7.5.6	Current work status and future works.....	99
8	Application and network function acceleration and offloading.....	101
8.1	Accelerated CU-UP on SmartNIC	101
8.1.2	Design and implementation.....	103
8.1.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	104
8.1.4	Limitations and future plans.....	105
8.2	Offloading of security network functions to Bluefield NICs	105
8.2.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art.....	106
8.2.2	Design and implementation.....	106
8.2.3	Usage and interfaces.....	107
8.2.4	Results, limitations and future plans.....	108
8.3	Accelerated Neural Network Execution.....	109
8.3.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art.....	109
8.3.2	Implementation.....	110
8.3.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	111
8.3.4	Evaluation.....	112
8.3.5	Limitations and further plans.....	113
8.4	Remote hardware accelerators in applications with vAccel	114
8.4.1	Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art.....	114
8.4.2	Implementation.....	115
8.4.3	Usage and Interfaces.....	115
8.4.4	Evaluation.....	116
8.4.5	Limitations and further plans.....	116

8.5	Tofino implementation of PREOF	117
8.5.1	Implementation.....	118
8.5.2	Evaluation.....	120
9	Conclusion	122
10	References.....	123
11	Annex 1	129

List of Figures

Figure 1: DESIRE6G Architecture and layers (see Section 2.1 of [2]).....	19
Figure 2: Service response latency for various container runtimes.....	23
Figure 3: IML Local NFVO overview	26
Figure 4: NF Routing between Containerized NFs – Normal mode.....	28
Figure 5: NF Routing between containerized NFs – Performance MODE.....	29
Figure 6: UE2ServiceMapper Packet processing steps.....	32
Figure 7: Simple NF routing data plane pipeline.....	34
Figure 8: load optimizer overview.....	37
Figure 9: Heavy hitter offloading in LO-DP.....	39
Figure 10: State migration from non-HH to HH instance.....	40
Figure 11: migration from HH to non-HH instance.....	41
Figure 12: Migration of key k from a nonHH instance to a HH instance with dynamic states.....	42
Figure 13: Testbed setup for the evaluation of Lo-DP (LO-CP runs on the CPU of the Tofino switch).....	44
Figure 14: Time of Dynamic state migrations between two NF-DP instances.....	45
Figure 15: IML Control Plane proxy hiding data plane optimizations.....	47
Figure 16: Overview of the P4-MTAGG meta-compiler.....	53
Figure 17: Overview of the Aggregated pipeline.....	55
Figure 18: Individual P4 pipeline performance (BARS represent NDR, latency is marked with red horizontal lines).....	56
Figure 19: Mixed traffic in aggregated pipelines.....	57
Figure 20: Example Throughput-Value-Function (TVF) and resource sharing example with the ppv framework.....	61
Figure 21: P4 implementation of the PV marker	63
Figure 22: Testbed setup.....	67
Figure 23: P4 Marker with 8000 silver UDP flows.....	67
Figure 24: Architecture of the agents.....	72
Figure 25: Network topology for INT.....	77
Figure 26: Telemetry header structure.....	78

Figure 27: Packet structure	82
Figure 28: INT headers.....	83
Figure 29: P4 pipeline architecture.....	84
Figure 30: Traffic capture in the experiment, with ingress traffic (no INT) in the top and augmented traffic in the bottom.....	87
Figure 31: Telemetry collector Architecture.....	92
Figure 32: Overview of the monitoring process.....	96
Figure 33: The two patching methods.....	98
Figure 34: Blocks data extraction breakdown.....	98
Figure 35: Overview of the Design of XDP-based CU-UP (uplink path).....	104
Figure 36: Security function offloading: 5GDAD architecture.....	106
Figure 37: SOL Server interactions	111
Figure 38: Sol server endpoints.....	112
Figure 39: DetNet protocol stack.....	117
Figure 40: PREF logical scenario.....	119
Figure 41: PEOF logical scenario.....	120

List of Tables

Table 1: NF pipelines with different complexity.....	56
Table 2: RTT measurements.....	88
Table 3: SOL benchmarking.....	113
Table 4: vAccel evaluation results.....	116
Table 5: Test results on the Packet Replication and Elimination functionalities.....	121

List of Acronyms

AAN	Access Aggregation Network
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
AQM	Active Queue Management
BFRT	Barefoot Runtime
CE	Congestion Experienced/Encountered
CNF	Containerized Network Function
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CU	Central Unit
CU-UP	Central Unit User Plane
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DetNet	Deterministic Networking
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DU	Distributed Unit
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
ECN	Explicit Congestion Notification
FAR	Forward Action Rule
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FQ	Fair Queueing
GPP	Generic-Purpose Processor
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling protocol

HH	Heavy Hitter
HLIR	High-Level Intermediate Representation
HQoS	Hierarchical Quality of Service
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IML	Infrastructure Management Layer
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
IP	Internet Protocol
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
LNSD	Local Network Service Descriptor
LO	Load Optimizer
LO-CP	Load Optimizer Control Plane
LO-DP	Load Optimizer Data Plane
LPM	Longest Prefix Match
MAS	Multi Agent System
ML	Machine Learning
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
MPLS-TE	MPLS-Traffic Engineering
MPPS	Million Packet Per Second
NIC	Network Interface Card
NDR	Non-Drop Rate
NF	Network Function
NF-CP	Network Function Control Plane
NF-DP	Network Function Data Plane
NFR	NF Routing
NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
P4RT	P4Runtime
P4S	P4 Switch
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDR	Packet Detection Rule

PDU	Packet Data Unit
PFA	Per-Flow Aggregation
PPV	Per Packet Value
PREOF	Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions
PV	Packet Value
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RT	Real Time
RU	Radio Unit
SDAP	Service Data Adaptation Protocol
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDNC	SDN Controller
SECaaS	Security as a Service
SF	Service Function
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SM	State Migration
T4P4S	Transpiler for P4 Switches
TNA	Tofino Native Architecture
UPF	User Plane Function
VES	VNF Event Streaming
VF	Virtual Function
VIM	Virtualized Infrastructure Manager
VNF	Virtual Network Function
QoS	Quality of Service
XDP	eXpress Data Path

Executive Summary

This document extends D4.1 [1] with special focus on the implementation details of components developed in WP4 and used in the unified programmable data plane layer of DESIRE6G. The document reflects the work done from month 12 to month 23. We first discuss how the different components described in this deliverable can be mapped to the architecture detailed in D2.2 [2]. Then, the implementation details of the component prototypes are documented in six main sections.

Key contributions

Key contributions in this document are the following:

- We show the mapping of components developed in WP4 to the DESIRE6G architecture detailed in D2.2 [2]. We describe the role and place of these components in the programmable data plane and physical infrastructure layers of the architecture.
- We introduce the initial prototype components including implementation details, preliminary evaluation results, analysis of limitations (performance and security) and plans for further developments handling the limitations:
 - Enhanced VIM and IML-Local NFVO, the components used for partial service deployment on the resources of a DESIRE6G site (Section 3)
 - Infrastructure network functions used for assigning packets to network services and steering packets through network functions according to the forwarding graph of the network service (Section 4)
 - Cloud-native mechanisms used in the unified programmable data plane layer of DESIRE6G to separate control and data planes, allow seamless optimization in the data plane and multi-tenant usage of hardware data planes (Section 5)
 - Traffic management methods to support performance isolation and deep slicing (Section 6)
 - Pervasive monitoring components providing extended and real-time visibility of the infrastructure (Section 7)
 - Different methods to accelerate application and network functions by offloading them to hardware accelerators (Section 8)

1 Introduction

This document serves as an interim report and an extension of D4.1 [1], focusing on the implementation aspects of the unified data plane layer introduced in the DESIRE6G architecture. It outlines the development conducted in WP4 of the project during months 12 to 23. WP4 has worked closely with WP2, and this deliverable incorporates the requirements and overall architecture defined in WP2.

The primary objective of this deliverable is to detail the implementation of components forming the end-to-end unified data plane layer of DESIRE6G. It includes preliminary evaluation results, identifies current limitations, and outlines plans for further improvements. The components discussed were largely defined in D4.1, and their early versions were published in MS4.2 [3]. This document reflects the current state of these components. The latest versions' source code will be publicly available on Zenodo and/or the project's GitHub repository with MS4.3 by the end of December 2024.

Section 2 identifies the role of the developed data plane and hardware accelerator components within the DESIRE6G architecture detailed in D2.2 [2].

The components are then presented in six main sections, each reflecting their specific roles and functions. Section 3 describes two components, the Enhanced VIM and the Local NFVO, which are involved in deploying network services at a DESIRE6G site. These components manage the resources of a single site, encompassing computational resources with hardware accelerators and a small data center.

Section 4 focuses on data plane components referred to as infrastructure network functions (NFs), which are critical for realizing the network service subgraph deployed at a DESIRE6G site by the SMO. These NFs handle UE-to-service assignment, routing across NF chains, and tunneling between DESIRE6G sites via the transport network.

The cloud-native model is widely regarded as an efficient approach to managing traditional computational tasks, as it automates service optimizations and simplifies user operations. However, traditional approaches cannot adequately address packet processing tasks with unique performance and latency requirements. Section 5 introduces various data plane techniques designed to support seamless optimization, enable multi-tenancy on hardware data planes, and enhance resource utilization.

These components are integral to the unified programmable data plane layer of DESIRE6G, facilitating the adaptation of cloud-native principles.

Performance isolation between slices, subslices, users, and other traffic classes is vital at both the management and data plane levels. Section 6 details programmable traffic management approaches that support a wide range of resource-sharing policies while ensuring low latency. These methods leverage the extended capabilities of programmable data planes.

Section 7 highlights monitoring components that provide critical data for decision-making tools like MAS, developed in WP3. These components extend visibility across the infrastructure, from real-time in-band network telemetry to software monitoring.

Section 8 explores components that utilize hardware accelerators to enhance throughput and latency performance. This section addresses the acceleration of both network and application functions.

Most sections assume that readers are already familiar with the DESIRE6G terminology and architecture design, as introduced in D2.2. Efforts have been made to avoid redundant repetition of content from prior deliverables (D2.2, D4.1) while ensuring the comprehensibility of this document.

2 Architecture and components of the unified programmable data plane

The final form of the DESIRE6G system architecture is described in [2]. The high-level view of the architecture is defined in Section 2.1 of [2] and is shown in Figure 1. It is basically identical with the architecture presented in deliverable D4.1 [1], with the difference that the main layers are also visualized. The main scope of WP4 is the E2E Programmable Data Plane (PDP) and the Physical Infrastructure Layer (the pink and grey layers in Figure 1), which is also defined in Section 2.1 of [2][1].

The components of the PDP layer defined and developed in the Desire6G project are the following:

- Infrastructure Management Layer (IML). It is responsible for transparent data plane optimization, hardware acceleration, and network and application function deployment, i.e., it is the bridge between the logical and the physical network function. The IML hides the implementation and deployment details of the NF-DP from the NF-CP by providing a simple unified view of the data plane. IML provides APIs towards the various upper layer entities. Besides, IML also includes components for data plane program deployment (see Section 3), which is generally referred to as “Enhanced VIM” and “Local NFVO” (not shown in the figure) whose structure is described in Figure 33 and Section 5.3 of [2]. Further, IML includes CP proxies for the configuration of the different Business NF-DPs (see Section 5.2) and Infrastructure NF-DPs (see Sections 5).
- The Infrastructure NF-DPs defined in the Desire6G project are the following:
 - o NF Routing (RR in Figure 1, see Section 4.2) that is responsible to implement the forwarding graph between NF-DPs in network services.
 - o Run-time Load Optimizer (see Section 5.1), consisting of a Load Balancer (LB) and a Heavy-hitter Offloader (HH)
 - o In-band Telemetry module (INT), that consists of a telemetry components at the transit nodes (e.g., PDP switches) and at the UE (see Section 7.3), as well as a Telemetry Collector (see Section 7.2)
 - o Specific Infra-DPs (not shown in the figure) that are deployed in all potential bottleneck NFs and are in charge of QoS enforcement.

- UE2ServiceMapper (see Section 4.1) that assigns the packets generated by UEs to the appropriate network service.
- TransportAdapter (see Section 5.4 of [2]) that ensures transport over various tunnelling protocols between DESIRE6G sites. TransportAdapter functions have been merged with NFRouting (see Section 4.2.2).
- Various Application Functions (AFs) that may be SOL-optimized (see Section 8)
- Besides, the PDP may include a PREOF component, which is a possible high-reliability realization to the Transport network, (see Section 8.5)

FIGURE 1: DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE AND LAYERS (SEE SECTION 2.1 OF [2])

3 Components for deployment and configuration of network service subgraphs

In this section, we describe two components that takes part in the deployment of the network service subgraph provided by the SMO in a given DESIRE6G site according to the processes detailed in D2.2. Enhanced VIM provides a container runtime infrastructure supporting the deployment of both containerized network functions (NFs) and application functions (AFs) on a Kubernetes cluster. It provides increased security and good performance. IML's Local NFVO subcomponent gets the deployment requests directly from the SMO. The service graph partition to be deployed on a DESIRE6G site may contain NFs and AFs, and the logical links between them, constituting a forwarding graph. IML's Local NFVO is responsible for the deployment of NFs and AFs using the Enhanced VIM or its in-built deployment scripts for hardware data plane targets. It also configures the interconnections between the different NF data plane components via NF Routing infrastructure functions. The configuration of other infrastructure functionalities (UE2Service Mapping, Transport adapter configuration in NF Routing) is also done by this component. Note that the scope of these components is restricted to a single DESIRE6G site where a pool of computational resources including data plane hardware is available.

3.1 Enhanced VIM

Our sandboxed container runtime infrastructure provides an advanced, highly secure, and efficient VIM solution tailored for DESIRE6G workloads. This integration comprises three main pillars: urunc, an ultra-lightweight container runtime optimized for unikernel-based workloads; bima, a specialized tool that packages unikernels into OCI-compatible artifacts; and kata-containers, an open-source project to which we actively contribute. Together, these pillars deliver a CRI-compatible, k8s-compatible VIM capable of securely managing and orchestrating containerized workloads across the continuum with ultra-low latency, rapid deployment, and secure isolation in shared infrastructure. The platform is designed for dynamic scaling and can leverage Knative-compatible features to provide scale-from-zero capability for on-demand services.

3.1.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

This VIM infrastructure brings several innovations to the ecosystem:

Hybrid Sandboxing and Isolation: Leveraging both unikernel-based containers (through urunc) and VM-level isolation (through kata-containers), this solution enables a layered approach to isolation, providing security for critical services and applications.

CRI and Knative Compatibility: Fully compatible with k8s Container Runtime Interface (CRI), our infrastructure also integrates seamlessly with Knative, enabling dynamic scaling of services from zero. This combination supports ultra-low-latency responses to fluctuating demand in cloud-native network services and applications.

Ultra-Fast Boot Times and Lightweight Execution: Unikernel-based workloads through urunc enable ultra-fast boot times, allowing for near-instantaneous startup and teardown of isolated instances. This low overhead makes the solution ideal for high-demand, ephemeral workloads.

Interoperability and Ease of Deployment: The use of OCI-compatible images (built via bima) for unikernels and generic container images for kata-containers, allows standardized and interoperable deployments, simplifying workload migration and enabling the secure execution of diverse services and applications across a heterogeneous environment.

3.1.2 Implementation

Our infrastructure integrates the following core components:

urunc: A unikernel-based container runtime that enables highly efficient, secure execution of sandboxed applications with low resource overhead and extremely fast boot times. urunc integrates directly into k8s via CRI, making it compatible with existing orchestration workflows. Urunc plugs in directly to high-level container runtimes (such as containerd), making it compatible with k8s, k3s and the rest of the orchestration tools in the cloud-native ecosystem.

bima: A custom tool that packages unikernels into OCI-compliant images, ensuring CRI compatibility and facilitating deployment across k8s environments. This enables applications to be built and packaged in an ultra-lightweight format, while facilitating software delivery.

kata-containers: A container runtime that uses lightweight VMs for security-enhanced isolation of containers, providing an additional layer of security suitable for sensitive telecom workloads. Our contributions to kata-containers enhance its isolation properties, by enabling the use of AWS Firecracker as the sandbox microVM, bringing both fast boot times, low-footprint sandboxing and enhanced security. At the same time, kata-containers bring CRI compatibility and improve resource efficiency for the execution of DESIRE6G workloads.

Knative Integration: This setup leverages Knative capabilities to enable scale-from-zero functionality, allowing for rapid scaling of workloads in response to network demand, particularly suited for microservices-based applications.

3.1.3 Usage and Interfaces

Our VIM infrastructure is designed with ease of deployment, management, and integration:

CRI-Compatible API: The infrastructure is fully compatible with k8s' CRI, enabling seamless management of unikernel and VM-based workloads. Applications can be deployed, monitored, and scaled through Kubernetes APIs, ensuring smooth integration with existing workflows.

Unified Interface for Sandboxed Workloads: Through urunc and kata-containers, and their compatibility with containerd, the same Kubernetes interface can deploy workloads as either unikernels, lightweight VMs, or generic containers, allowing for flexible isolation levels based on workload requirements.

Standardized Image Format via bima: Unikernels can be deployed as OCI-compatible images, which simplifies integration into existing CI/CD pipelines and allows for standardized lifecycle management, consistent with traditional containerized workloads.

Knative Compatibility: The Knative-compatible setup enables dynamic scaling, supporting applications that require on-demand scaling and burst workloads in a cloud-native environment.

3.1.4 Evaluation

Initial evaluation of kata-containers and urunc has been carried out in the context of a serverless application. Specifically, we measure the total response latency with a particular focus on the spawn

time of the function, when scaling from zero. The function is a simple httpreply application, packaged as a generic container and a unikernel. Figure 2 shows the roundtrip response latency for this function, for the various container runtimes installed on our local testbed. Preliminary results show that there is a trade-off between isolation and performance (generic vs kata-*), whereas urunc outperforms all sandboxed container runtimes, bringing the benefits of unikernel-based application spawn to generic containers.

FIGURE 2: SERVICE RESPONSE LATENCY FOR VARIOUS CONTAINER RUNTIMES

3.1.5 Limitations and further plans

Currently, the scope of urunc is limited to example applications/workloads. We plan to extend application availability and provide a more extensive evaluation, both in terms of resource consumption, as well as latency response.

The code for each component of this infrastructure is available via open-source repositories: 1) **urunc** and **bima**: Available at their respective open-source repositories¹². These repositories include documentation for unikernel packaging and deployment in Kubernetes environments. 2) **kata-containers**: kata-containers³ is a community-backed open-source project, under the umbrella of the OpenInfra foundation. Our contributions and enhancements are clearly documented and integrated upstream into the main project.

3.2 IML-Local Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator

The Local Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (Local NFVO) is a subcomponent of IML responsible for deploying a network function subgraph to a local site. The subgraph is provided in yaml format by the SMO and it describes the part of the network service to be implemented by the given DESIRE6G site and the transport network connections to other DESIRE6G sites. IML's Local NFVO is built on a Kubernetes-based VIM (e.g., Enhanced VIM) and Helm, with added support for deploying NFs onto hardware data planes such as Intel Tofino. For containerized network functions (NFs), Kubernetes is only used for pod deployment without utilizing the native autoscaling capabilities of Kubernetes. Cloud-native features like scaling are addressed by other (run-time) subcomponents of the IML, detailed in Section 5. Note we call this component as Local NFVO as its role similar to the NFVO in ETSI specification, but its scope is limited to manage resources in a single DESIRE6G site. The interfaces of our early prototype are also simplified.

¹ <https://github.com/nubificus/urunc>

² <https://github.com/nubificus/bima>

³ <https://github.com/kata-containers/kata-containers>

3.2.1 Implementation

The implementation leverages the following technologies:

- **Kubernetes (k8s):** Acts as the container orchestrator, managing cluster deployments. Each NF is encapsulated as a pod within the cluster.
- **Helm:** Serves as a Kubernetes package manager, utilizing templating for deployment configurations through Helm charts, which are based on Go templates.
- **Flannel:** Provides a basic L3 overlay network used for the management network. No Flannel-specific features are utilized.
- **Multus:** A CNI meta-plugin that enables Kubernetes pods to attach additional interfaces through network-attachment-definitions leveraging CNI plugins.
- **SR-IOV (Single Root I/O Virtualization):** Facilitates sharing a single PCIe device using virtual functions (VFs) for inter-node communication. It operates through the SR-IOV CNI and SR-IOV Device plugins.

3.2.1.1 Networking Infrastructure

The NF Routing (NFR) component, a specialized infrastructure NF (see Section 4.2), is deployed on each node in a dedicated pod (one instance per node) and interconnected using SR-IOV VFs. Each NF pod interfaces with its respective node's NFR via a L2 virtual link (currently using veth pairs managed via the Bridge CNI plugin). The per node NFR instance relies on the DPDK-based P4 [4] backend called T4P4S [5]. The IP and MAC addresses of the pods are statically assigned.

3.2.1.2 Network Function Deployment Process

The deployment process begins with the local network service descriptor (LNSD) (see D2.2), which contains:

- Kubernetes manifests for each NF
- A list of links representing the NF graph structure.

Using this information, the IML's Local NFVO dynamically populates the values.yaml file with variables needed for the Helm chart used for the templating of the deployment. Each NF's deployment manifest

is further customized and extended using Helm’s templating engine to incorporate desired parameters and connections.

The templated Helm chart is then deployed to provision the network function graph defined in the network service descriptor provided by the SMO. The SR-IOV configuration ensures high-performance inter-node communication, while Multus facilitates attaching additional network interfaces to support multi-interface NFs.

This design balances containerized deployment flexibility with the low-latency and high-throughput requirements of hardware-accelerated data planes. It seamlessly integrates Kubernetes’ orchestration capabilities with the specialized needs of programmable hardware like Intel Tofino.

FIGURE 3: IML LOCAL NFVO OVERVIEW

As seen in Figure 3, Helm creates the actual manifest and network config of the pods using the manifest templates and input from the SMO. The pods are using images from the image registry (yellow area in the figure).

After getting the subgraph as a local network service descriptor (LNSD) from the SMO, IML’s local NFVO assigns resources to the various NFs. Some NFs may have identical implementations for different

hardware targets. After the assignment phase, the component deploys the NF-DPs, NF-CPs and AFs on the selected targets. Control planes and applications are always deployed on the site-local Kubernetes cluster. However, NF-DPs may be deployed on various targets (e.g., x86 as containerized network function (CNF), Intel Tofino, smart NIC). P4-based data planes can be deployed as CNFs on a Kubernetes cluster using a special image prepared with the DPDK-based P4 switch called T4P4S [5], or can be directly executed on an Intel Tofino dedicated for data plane acceleration. The image that is used on the Tofino is containing P4 code compatible with the target. The deployment on hardware data planes is implemented by target-specific deployment scripts that cover the P4-code compilation, binary loading and execution processes.

An example for a CNF description in the values.yaml file can be seen below. The roles of the various fields are also described in comments:

```

nf-1:
  name: "nf-1"           // NF identifier
  image: "desire6g/nf1:stable" // Image to use
  node: "node1"         // Which node to deploy
  mac: "aa:bb:cc:dd:ee:ff" // MAC address to use
  ip: "192.168.0.10/24" // Static IP address
  hugepages-1Gi: "2Gi" // Further resources to be used
  memory: "2Gi"

```

In addition to the NF and AF deployment, the component also prepares the configuration of infrastructure network functions like NFR. In case of CNFs, this process includes the creation of virtual L2 links between the NF-DP instances and the host-specific NFR instance. Each host in the Kubernetes cluster has a host-specific NFR instance implementing the forwarding graph.

An example for the host-specific containerized NFR configuration in values.yaml:

```

nfrovers:
  image: "desire6g/nfrouter:stable" // Image to use
  hugepages-1Gi: "2Gi"             // Resources to be used
  memory: "2Gi"
  nodes:                            // Each node to deploy to and
  - name: "node1"                   // the MAC addresses of the VF-s
    vf-macs: ["aa:bb:cc:dd:ee:ff"]
  - name: "node2"
    vf-macs: ["bb:bb:cc:dd:ee:ff"]
  links:                             // The description of the NF graph
  - from: "nf-1"                    // with links
    to: "nf-2"
  - from: "nf-2"
    to: "nf-1"

```

The manifests generated from the above configurations can be seen in Annex 1.

3.2.2 Evaluation

FIGURE 4: NF ROUTING BETWEEN CONTAINERIZED NFs - NORMAL MODE

As seen in Figure 4, the scenario is the following: NF-1 and NF-2 are deployed on Node 1 and NF-3 on Node 2. NF-1 is the iperf client and NF-2 and NF-3 is the iperf server. With this setup we can measure inter-pod connection between NF-1 and NF-2 and inter-node connection between NF-2 and NF-3. The NFs are connected to the node's NF Routing instance using veth pairs over L2 bridges and the NF Routing instances on each node are connected through the NIC's VFs. Preliminary testing with iperf shows both inter-pod and inter-node communications achieve around 1Gbps throughput with this "normal mode" deployment setup.

FIGURE 5: NF ROUTING BETWEEN CONTAINERIZED NFS – PERFORMANCE MODE

We designed a “performance mode” deployment setup as well, as seen in Figure 5. In this mode, there is only one NF Routing instance in the cluster, deployed on a high performance P4-capable switch (Intel Tofino) instead of on each Kubernetes node. This way, every NF pod is communicating through SR-IOV VFs with the NF Routing instance. Preliminary testing with iperf shows that two pods on separate nodes connected directly with VFs can achieve around 90 Gbps throughput using a 100 Gbps capable NIC.

3.2.3 Limitations and further plans

The current implementation has identified potential performance bottlenecks, primarily attributed to the use of veth pairs for connecting NF pods to the node’s NFR infrastructure. While veth pairs provide a straightforward mechanism for linking containers, they introduce overhead due to kernel-based packet processing and context switching, which may degrade throughput and increase latency. To address this, ongoing work focuses on transitioning from kernel-based networking to userspace networking technologies, including:

- Vector Packet Processing (VPP): A high-performance, userspace packet processing framework that eliminates kernel overhead by handling packets directly in user space.
- Memif Interfaces: Memory interfaces designed for efficient communication between VPP and containers. Memif enables zero-copy packet processing, reducing latency and improving throughput compared to veth pairs and traditional L2 bridges.

This shift aims to leverage VPP's performance advantages while maintaining compatibility with Kubernetes-managed deployments. By integrating memif, the solution can achieve better resource utilization and performance, especially for latency-sensitive applications.

In addition to replacing veth pairs, we are exploring the feasibility of using NIC subfunctions (SFs) instead of traditional virtual functions (VFs) for inter-node communication. SFs provide a finer-grained approach to virtualizing network interfaces compared to VFs, potentially improving isolation, resource allocation, and compatibility with emerging hardware acceleration features. These optimization efforts aim to ensure that the deployment framework scales effectively and meets the stringent performance requirements of the DESIRE6G unified data plane layer.

We also plan to integrate P4 code generation tools like P4RRROT [6] that aims at supporting application logic (e.g., sensor stream processing, low level control processes) offloading to the data plane. P4RRROT has the advantage that the same P4RRROT project (i.e., the image) consisting of Python codes and P4 templates can directly be transformed into a P4 program working with multiple targets. P4RRROT currently supports both software and hardware targets (Intel Tofino and Netronome Agilio).

This subcomponent of IML currently provides a simple REST API without authentication. As this component plays a crucial role in managing site-local resources and network configurations, a security layer needs to be added to it in the future.

4 Infrastructure network functions for network service execution

Infrastructure network functions are data plane elements that ensures packet forwarding and processing according to the network service definition of DESIRE6G. These elements are part of the proposed DESIRE6G infrastructure and responsible for three tasks: 1) assignment of packets to a network service, 2) forwarding packets along a chain of network functions according to the service graph, and 3) tunnelling between DESIRE6G sites interconnected with a transport network. These elements rely on a special DESIRE6G header detailed in D2.2 [2]. The infrastructure network functions are configured and controlled by the Local NFVO subcomponent of IML. In this deliverable, we mostly focus on the implementation details of these data plane components. The high-level control plane interfaces (REST APIs) have already been detailed in D2.2.

4.1 UE2ServiceMapper

UE2ServiceMapper is an infrastructure NF in DESIRE6G. Its main role is to map the traffic from a specific user to a specific service and RAN site the UE is connected to. In downlink direction, it maps the destination IP address (or other UE identifier) of incoming packets to a service id and RAN site location id. In downlink case, it is deployed at the first DESIRE6G site where the packet enters the DESIRE6G network domain. In case of a broadband Internet service, it is in the mobile core after the Internet gateway. In case of an end-to-end service, it is deployed near the application function generating traffic towards the UE or other application functions in the DESIRE6G domain. The current implementation creates and fills a DESIRE6G header with service id and RAN site location id and the id of the next NF to be applied in the forwarding graph of the network service and adds it to the packets (right after the Ethernet header). Note that in downlink direction this component has a role like the Packet Detection Rules (PDRs) and Forward Action Rules (FARs) in the 5G UPF. In uplink direction, the component is

deployed in RAN sites and assigns the packet to a network service and fills the RAN site location. Note that in this case, filling the RAN site location field in the DESIRE6G header is trivial and can be done without user classification, reducing the memory and computational overhead of this component at RAN sites.

4.1.1 Implementation

The UE2ServiceMapper has been implemented in P4 for both v1model and TNA architectures. The hardware-accelerated TNA-based implementation supports two execution mode: a Tofino only when all the UEs are served by a single instance and hybrid mode which distributes UEs to be handled between a hardware and one or more software instances, enabling to support much larger number of UEs.

FIGURE 6: UE2SERRVICEMAPPER PACKET PROCESSING STEPS

The pipeline depicted in Figure 6 starts with ModeSelector table that determines the traffic direction (i.e., upstream or downstream) and extracts the UE identifier (e.g., source or destination IPv6/IPv4 address) from the packet. Note that this is a small table whose parameters are configured at deployment time. Then, the ServiceMapping table is executed that uses the traffic direction and the UE identifier to set the service id and the id of the first network function to be reached in the network service. We assume that each network service in DESIRE6G has its own IP prefix so that the table only stores a limited

number of LPM entries. Finally, the LocationMapping table is executed that maps each UE identifier to a RAN site location id. In upstream case, this mapping is simple as the RAN site location is static. However, in the downstream case, the LocationMapping table may have as many entries as UEs we have in the system. In case of a large number of UEs, hardware switches like Intel Tofino may have not enough SRAM resources. To solve this issue, we added the isHH helper table to identify heavy users/UEs having large throughput demand. These UEs are served by the hardware switch by applying the local LocationMapping table, while non-heavy users are served by a software instance running the simplified version of the same P4 program. The UE2ServiceMapper also has a local control plane that provides a REST API as a northbound interface and communicate with the HW/SW switches via P4Runtime. The northbound interfaces of the service have been described in D2.2.

4.2 NF Routing

NF Routing (NFR) is a key component of the PDP layer. The component processes the DESIRE6G header and implements the forwarding logic of network service graphs. It is a special router that uses the service id, location id and nextNF id to steer the packets towards the responsible NF. In addition to routing, NF Routing is responsible for resolving the nextNF id when an NF finished with the packet's processing.

4.2.1 Implementation

The data plane part of NF Routing was implemented in P4 for both Tofino and software (v1model) targets. The data plane pipeline shown in Figure 7 applies two tables in sequence.

FIGURE 7: SIMPLE NF ROUTING DATA PLANE PIPELINE

NF Router expects packets with a valid DESIRE6G header. It first applies the FWDGExecute table that implements the transitions between NF data planes in the network service graph. If the packet comes in from an NF data plane instance, the NF Routing sets the next NF where the packet needs to be forwarded according to the service graph. This table uses the ingress port on which the packet is received and optionally can use the vlan tag field in the Ethernet header to determine if the packet is directly sent by a NF data plane instance or another NF Routing instance. In cases when two NF Routing instances are connected to each other, the second instance does not update the nextNF, skipping the FWDGExecute table. The second table in the pipeline is NFRouter that simply forwards the packet according to the service id, location id and the nextNF id in the DESIRE6G header to the appropriate NF data plane instance. The action in the table sets the egress port of the switch and the destination MAC address to reach the NF data plane instance with the nextNF id. NF Routing function is also responsible to remove the DESIRE6G header if the packet leaves the DESIRE6G domain, e.g., before terminating in an application function or going towards the Internet. It is implemented by a special action in the NFRouter table.

NF Routing also has a local control plane that provides a REST API as a northbound interface and communicate with the HW/SW switches via P4Runtime. The northbound interfaces of the service have already been described in D2.2.

4.2.2 Transport adapter functions

Transport adapter is the infrastructure NF responsible for interconnecting different DESIRE6G sites. This component implements different tunnelling protocols like GTP over the transport network between two

DESIRE6G sites. In previous deliverables, we assumed that Transport adapter is a separate infrastructure NF that is deployed on one or more gateway nodes of the DESIRE6G site. In the current implementation, we added this functionality to the NFR component implemented as a new action in the NFRouter table. Currently, we only support GTP encapsulation and decapsulation.

4.3 Integration into IML's Local NFVO

IML has both deployment time and runtime functions. The deployment of a network service subgraph provided by the SMO on a DESIRE6G site is managed by the Local NFVO component of IML as described in Section 3.2. In addition to the creation of CNFs and the deployment of NFs on hardware data planes, the local NFVO is also responsible for the configuration of infrastructure NFs already deployed in a DESIRE6G site. The Local NFVO also connects NFs and AFs to various NF Routing instances via virtual L2 links. NF Routing function is implemented on each DESIRE6G site, but UE2ServiceMapping function is only implemented by selected sites where the traffic enters the DESIRE6G domain and packets need to be assigned to services, etc. As described in D2.2, both infrastructure components provide simple REST-based configuration APIs. These APIs are directly used by IML to load rules 1) at deployment time, 2) when a new UE is attached or detached to/from the service, 3) when the NF instances change or 4) when the UE location changes.

4.4 Limitations and further plans

Current implementations of infrastructure NFs relies on the non-standard DESIRE6G header. In the next phase of the project, we will investigate how the information stored DESIRE6G header can be stored in IPv6 headers, applying technologies like SRv6 or its micro-SID approach [7] and how standard SRv6 routing methods could replace DESIRE6G's NF Routing mechanism.

5 Cloud-native data plane components

In this section, we overview the different components developed in DESIRE6G to support the cloud-native handling of data plane resources. The section focuses on the implementation of three main cloud-native features: 1) hiding data plane deployment details by IML's control plane proxy, 2) seamless optimization in the data plane solved by the run-time load optimizer, and 3) enable multitenant usage/virtualization of P4 programmable data planes by data plane program aggregation.

5.1 Run-time Load Optimizer

In the pursuit of a cloud-native, unified implementation of the data plane, we address the complexity of physical network deployments, which typically involve multiple instances of network functions (NFs). For efficient traffic steering among these instances, load balancers are essential. In order to unify and simplify the interaction between the control plane and the data plane while abstracting implementation details, we propose a Load Optimizer (LO) method that comprises two components: the Load Optimizer Control Plane (LO-CP) and the Load Optimizer Data Plane (LO-DP). Currently, the LO-CP is implemented separately, but in the next phase of the project it will be integrated into the control plane proxy of IML. LO-CP acts as a control plane proxy within the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML) and is responsible for configuring and managing the NF instances and load balancing rules between them. LO-CP can dynamically adjust the number of NF instances, perform state migration and configure the LO-DP. To effectively manage the diverse traffic demands within the unified data plane, the Load Optimizer (LO) method also targets the challenge of handling Heavy Hitter (HH) users—traffic groups that require significantly higher throughput than their Non-Heavy Hitter (non-HH) counterparts, balancing the users' load between hardware and software instances of the same NF data plane. Figure 8 overviews the different components of the proposed method.

FIGURE 8: LOAD OPTIMIZER OVERVIEW

5.1.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Current related works [8][9][10] do not fully address the challenges associated with efficiently managing heterogeneous environments of multiple instances of network functions and their deployment across diverse data plane implementations, particularly when it comes to dynamically mapping traffic flows to the appropriate NF instances. The load optimization method effectively addresses the following:

- **Dynamic Mapping:** Implementing a framework that dynamically allocates traffic to the most appropriate NF instances based on factors like real-time flow characteristics.
- **State Migration:** Enabling the transfer of the changing states of user's traffic (state migration) during runtime to different instances seamlessly while minimizing both state migration time and packet loss rates. It includes the migration of both static (e.g., lookup table entries) and dynamic (e.g., values stored in registers) states.
- **Unified View:** The optimization details (e.g., number of instances, type of instances, etc.) are hidden from the control plane entity of the NF.

5.1.2 Implementation

To effectively manage a substantial number of non-HH users, software-based NF data planes can be employed for efficient service delivery. However, the resource-intensive nature of HH traffic requires the deployment of hardware data planes, such as those operating on constrained platforms like Intel Tofino, with limited SRAM and TCAM capacity. We detail the three primary components of the proposed LO method: the LO-DP, the LO-CP, and the extension of NF-DP functionality needed for dynamic state migration.

5.1.2.1 Load Optimizer Data Plane (LO-DP)

LO-DP was implemented in P4 using both v1model and TNA architectures. It consists of two key mechanisms in the data plane: 1) heavy hitter offloading and 2) load balancing. Note that we assume that there is a heavy hitter detection NF [9][10] deployed on the network path (e.g., integrated into UE2Service Mapping) that fills the HH flag in the DESIRE6G header.

The heavy hitter offloading pipeline is depicted in Figure 9. After parsing the packet and extracting the extra fields from the DESIRE6G header (key representing the UE identifier the traffic belongs to, HH-flag showing if it is a heavy user or not) we first check the current HH state of the packet. After that we apply a lookup on the StoredHHState table with the key to get the previous HH-state known by the LO-DP component. Note if the new HH state and the previous state are not the same, it indicates that a HH packet group changed to non-HH or vice versa. Note that the StoredHHState table can be implemented efficiently as it only needs to store the list of HH UEs. If a key is not in the table, it is considered as non-HH. There are four different cases (from left to right in the figure):

- Both new and previous states are HH and we remove key from REG by 1) checking if $REG[hash[key]] == key$, 2) then $REG[hash(key)] = EXT$, where EXT is an unused extremal key value. This step is needed for handling situations when a non-HH packet group became HH. In this case the REG register was set for key, denoting that LO-CP had already been notified about the change in HH-state. If we left key in REG, the next change in the HH-state may not generate notification to LO-CP. Then LO-DP applies GetHHNode table to map key to the location/address of the HH-node dedicated for key.

- The new state is HH but the previous state was non-HH. In this case, we have to handle the change and before forwarding packets directly to the HH-node, we first have to prepare it (i.e., moving states from the non-HH NF instance to the HH-node, filling tables for key, etc.). To this end, LO-DP notifies LO-CP, but to avoid redundancy and large number of message generation, register REG keeps track if LO-CP has already notified or not. We first check the stored value (skey) in REG for key. If $skey=key$, LO-CP has already been notified, so we do not have to do anything, just forwarding the packet on the nonHH path. If skey does not equal to key, we store key value in REG for key, notify LO-CP and forward the packet on the non-HH path.
- The new state is non-HH but the previous state was HH. Similarly to the previous case, we have to notify LO-CP about the change in HH-state. REG is used in the same way to keep track if LO-CP has already been notified or not. At the end of this case, the GetHHNode lookup table returns the responsible HH-node and the packet is forwarded to it.
- Both new and previous states are non-HH. Similarly to the first case, we just remove key from REG and forward the packet on the non-HH path.

FIGURE 9: HEAVY HITTER OFFLOADING IN LO-DP

Forward packet on non-HH paths in the figure is implemented by a table that stores the non-HH instances where the lookup is performed according to a hash computed from the key.

In addition to traffic steering LO-DP is also responsible for receiving and forwarding the so-called State Migration (SM) packets sent by LO-CP to facilitate dynamic state migration between NF-DP instances. Notifications regarding the completion of dynamic state migrations are also received and forwarded to the LO-CP.

5.1.2.2 Load Optimizer Control Plane (LO-CP)

The main role of LO-CP is to handle static and dynamic state migrations between NF-DP instances. For NF-DPs with static states (e.g., entries stored in match-action tables), LO-CP can perform static state migration alone without the involvement of LO-DP and support of the NF-DP implementation. Note that LO-CP acts as a P4Runtime proxy between the NF-CP and the NF-DP instances and applies an extended northbound P4Runtime interface where each table entry is annotated with the load balancing key (UE identifier as defined above). Key is needed for the proper distribution of rules to among the different NF-DP instances. For NF-DPs with dynamic states (e.g., values stored in registers) that may be updated by each packet crossing the NF-DP instance, LO-CP oversees the migration of these register states to maintain consistency.

FIGURE 10: STATE MIGRATION FROM NON-HH TO HH INSTANCE

As described above, LO-DP notifies LO-CP about changes in the HH-state of a packet group belonging to key. LO-CP is responsible for moving states between non-HH and HH instances and prepare data

plane tables in LO-DP. In Figure 10, LO-CP gets a notification about that key K become HH. The previous state of key k was nonHH. Before using the HH path in the data plane, we have to prepare the HH instance of the implemented NF to be able to process the packet group of key K. After getting the notification, LO-CP moves states from nonHH instance to the HH one for key K. The states can either be read from the data plane instance of nonHH NF (step 2a) or be filled by the LO-CP from its local knowledge base (e.g., database). If the data plane instance of HH NF is prepared for handling packets of key K (step 2b), the HH path is activated in LO-DP (steps 3-7). Note that the old nonHH instance of the NF data plane can either be suspended or removed, depending on the system.

FIGURE 11: MIGRATION FROM HH TO NON-HH INSTANCE

LO-DP also sends a notification if key K becomes nonHH. The corresponding LO-CP process is described in Figure 11. Similarly to the previous case, after obtaining the notification, LO-CP moves states from HH instance to the nonHH instance handling packets of key K. The states can either be read from the data plane instance of HH NF (step 2a) or be filled by the LO-CP from its local knowledge base (e.g., database). Optionally, this step may require additional actions: revive or start the nonHH instance for key K. After the states on the nonHH path are configured, the nonHH path in LO-DP needs to be activated. To this end, we remove key K from the table storedHHstate and GetHHNode in steps 4-6. Finally, in step 7, we remove entries for key K from the data plane instance of HH NF.

In addition to the proxy function of LO-CP, it also aggregates the state of data plane counter objects to provide consistent values to the NF-CPs.

5.1.2.3 NF-DP functionality extension for supporting dynamic state migration

In contrast to static states that can be easily migrated by LO-CP, dynamic states stored in registers can change from one packet to another packet. To keep consistency, we also require additional functionalities to be implemented by NF-DPs. We assume that the dynamic states are linked to packet groups of key k and there are no global dynamic states that need to be synchronized. As shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, LO-CP handles state transition from one instance of NF-DP to another when a packet group of key k changed its HH-state from nonHH to HH or vice versa. The static state transitions can be done by LO-CP, as they are not changing frequently. However, dynamic states (e.g., stored in registers) updated by packet arrivals cannot be moved through the control plane in a consistent way, since control plane processes work at a much longer timescales (1-10ms) than the packet processing times (10-1000ns). To solve this issue, we propose a slight extension to the NF-DP instance implementations. NF-DPs needs to support: 1) the handling of so called StateMigration (SM) packets, 2) functions for storing/encoding states of a packet group denoted by key k into the SM packet, 3) functions for restoring/loading states of the packet group key k to the data plane objects (e.g., registers) from the SM packet, 4) ability to forward data packets to another NF-DP instance (HH or nonHH) without processing it, and 5) the ability to send notification to LO-CP.

FIGURE 12: MIGRATION OF KEY K FROM A NONHH INSTANCE TO A HH INSTANCE WITH DYNAMIC STATES

Figure 12 denotes the additional packet processing steps introduced for handling state migration process; the thicker arrows show the main steps of dynamic state migration:

1. When LO-CP moves states from nonHH to HH NF-DP for key k. It first loads static rules for key k to the HH NF-DP.
2. Then if NF-DP does not have dynamic states, the process is finished.
3. If dynamic states need to be moved between the two instances, LO-CP generates an “empty” State Migration (SM) packet for moving the states of key k and sends it to the nonHH instance (active instance for key k).
4. In the nonHH NF-DP, the SM packet triggers that the instance is switched to forwarding mode (for packet group of key k), fill the SM packet with dynamic state information (register contents), and forward SM packet to the HH NF-DP (passive instance).
5. In forwarding mode, the NF-DP instance only forwards data packets to the HH instance, instead of performing the NF-DP logic. In this way, it avoids further changes in the dynamic states.
6. When the “filled” SM packet arrives to the HH instance, HH NF-DP switches to non-forwarding mode (for packet groups of key k) and loads the dynamic states into data plane objects (e.g., registers) from the SM packet. After that it sends a notification to LO-CP about the completion of state transitions.
7. The SM packet can be dropped or used as notification message to LO-CP, depending on the implementation.

The current state of implementation:

- 1) LO-DP implemented in P4 for both v1model and TNA architectures.
- 2) LO-CP implemented in Python for both v1model and Tofino. For Tofino, it currently uses BFRT API.
- 3) Example Firewall NF extended with handling SM packets implemented in P4 for both TNA and v1model architecture. V1model version can be executed with the T4P4S DPDK backend on CPU targets.

5.1.3 Usage and Interfaces

Currently, a LO installation (both LO-DP and LO-CP) is assigned to a specific NF used in one of the network services. In LO-DP, the configuration is performed via BFRT (will be replaced by P4Runtime in

the future). LO-CP acts as a proxy between the NF's control plane and its data plane instances. LO-CP provides a northbound BFRT API for the NF-CP and connects to the NF-DP instances via BFRT too. The northbound interface is extended as each table entry is annotated with a load balancing key (key in the above algorithm descriptions). Key is needed for the proper distribution of rules to among the different NF-DP instances. The need for supporting dynamic state migration is set at installation time.

5.1.4 Evaluation

FIGURE 13: TESTBED SETUP FOR THE EVALUATION OF LO-DP (LO-CP RUNS ON THE CPU OF THE TOFINO SWITCH)

The evaluation was conducted in a dedicated testing environment shown in Figure 13, utilizing an Intel Tofino switch with four pipelines and two x86 servers (AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3970X 32-Core Processor, 3.7GHz, 128GB RAM) acting as a traffic generator and a K8S cluster running the containerized NF. Each pipeline of the Tofino switch runs different P4 programs. Two pipelines are employed: Pipe-1 for the LO-DP implementation and Pipe-2 for the NF-DP instance handling the traffic of Heavy Hitter (HH) users. In the K8S cluster, we run a single instance of the NF-DP program with the DPDK-based (Data Plane Development Kit) P4 compiler and software switch framework called T4P4S. This instance only uses a single CPU core. The role of this instance is to handle the traffic load of Non-Heavy Hitter (non-HH) users. This setup allows for a comprehensive assessment of the efficiency and performance of the proposed load balancing strategy. In the evaluation scenario, a HH user becomes a non-HH and thus its states are moved from the Tofino-based NF-DP instance to the software instance. The NF-DP we use is a simple stateful firewall implemented for both v1model and TNA. Note that the test traffic was

generated by the Traffic Generator server on one of its 100Gbps ports. After the NF execution was completed, the packets were forwarded back to the Traffic Generator node on the other 100Gbps port.

1. State Migration (SM) Time Measurement:

The SM time was measured from the moment the controller received a digest indicating a state change until the completion of the state migration process. This time includes the static state migration managed by LO-CP, the generation of dynamic state migration packet, its forwarding between the two instances and the notification sent to the LO-CP about the completion of the migration process. The CDF of migration times measured for 100 state migrations are depicted in Figure 14.

FIGURE 14: TIME OF DYNAMIC STATE MIGRATIONS BETWEEN TWO NF-DP INSTANCES

One can see that the state migration times were below 50ms in all cases with a median of 35.5ms. The most significant factors in the state migration times are the generation of state migration packets in the Python-based LO-CP and the saving of new states in the software instance.

2. NF latency and throughput:

We also performed measurements to check the latency packets experience during the NF execution. We used the in-built latency measurement feature of TREX to sample the packet latency between sending out the packet and its reception. The traffic volume was set according to the maximum non-drop rate (i.e., max. rate with 0% packet loss). When we used the hardware instance of the NF running

on the Tofino ASIC, the latency was 4 usec in average with 0 usec jitter, the maximum delay was 9 usec. If the load optimizer data plane forwarded the packets to the software instance running on the x86 server, the average latency increased to 15usec with 3usec jitter and 50usec maximum delay. The increase was caused by the CPU-based processing as the propagation delay was negligible in our setup. The non-drop rate for the hardware instance was 100 Gbps, the line rate. For the software instance with a single CPU core, it was 9Gbps with packet size of 1500Bytes. We also tested the software instance with different packet sizes, resulting in 9 Gbps (1.4 MPPS) and 8.1 Gbps (12.7 MPPS) for 800 bytes and 80 bytes packet sizes, resp.

5.1.5 Limitations and further plans

Though the initial evaluations are promising, more complex scenarios need to be examined to draw final conclusions about the method's performance and viability under realistic workload. The interaction between the LO-DP and LO-CP could introduce latency during instance migration. The current implementation applies a simple load balancing method for non-HH instances. Migration of active flows (e.g., TCP) could cause packet reordering that may affect the flows performance (i.e., throughput degradation). Enabling state migration at flowlet boundaries (i.e., passive period of a flow) could help in keeping packet ordering. This mechanism will be implemented in the final phase of the project. Future work will also focus on optimizing the tagging process for better performance, enhancing the algorithms in LO-DP to handle diverse traffic patterns, and simplifying the integration of components to facilitate easier deployment and management in real-world scenarios. We will also integrate the functionality of LO-CP into IML's control plane proxy. The method relies on the HH-flag and key (user id) carried by the DESIRE6G header. A potential security issue may be if an attacker falsifies these header fields in the network. We assume that each DESIRE6G site is a private network while communication between DESIRE6G sites is carried out over encrypted tunnels. Security issues related to the DESIRE6G header, and the carried packet-level incentives will be investigated more deeply in the next phase of the project.

5.2 IML-Control Plane Proxy

IML's Control Plane Proxy serves as a separation layer between the data and control planes of packet processing NFs as depicted in Figure 15. Its primary role is to enable data plane optimization, including rearrangement, aggregation, or disaggregation of P4 programs in a manner that remains invisible to the

control planes of the NFs. Additionally, it introduces a persistency layer, ensuring that even if the data plane structure is modified, the control plane does not need to re-upload the active match-action table entries or reconfigure other data plane objects.

By achieving these objectives, the proxy facilitates the decomposition of network functionalities into smaller, modular elements. Instead of maintaining a single large P4 program, smaller functions, and their corresponding controllers can be created and combined as needed. The proxy also stores data plane configuration states for NF data planes (e.g., active table entries, counter states, etc.). When rearrangements occur, these stored configurations are seamlessly re-applied to the data plane using a repetition method, ensuring that changes are imperceptible to both the control plane and end users.

FIGURE 15: IML CONTROL PLANE PROXY HIDING DATA PLANE OPTIMIZATIONS

5.2.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

FlowVisor [11] is a pivotal tool in the OpenFlow [12] ecosystem, enabling hardware virtualization and isolating control plane access in SDN. By acting as a transparent proxy between OpenFlow controllers and network switches, FlowVisor partitions the underlying physical network into multiple virtual networks. Each virtual network, or slice, operates independently and is managed by its respective controller, facilitating multi-tenancy and resource sharing without compromising isolation.

Currently, there is no direct equivalent of FlowVisor for P4 data planes, but similar tools and frameworks like P4Visor [13] exist to enable data plane virtualization, multi-tenancy, and control plane isolation in P4-based systems. These tools are however limited to BMv2 and not actively developed and do not support data plane optimizations we target. The IML Control Plane Proxy integrates multiple use cases and hides data plane transformations like load balancing, aggregation, disaggregation, heavy hitter handling. Initial results on the control plane proxy have been reported in [14][15].

5.2.2 Implementation

Each control plane proxy initiates a set of gRPC servers and clients used for P4Runtime messaging. The NF control planes connect to the servers, where the proxy emulates a network node. Meanwhile, the clients within the proxy connect to the P4Runtime interface of data plane hardware or software switches, presenting themselves as controllers to these nodes.

In case of data plane program aggregation and disaggregation, data plane object identifiers within P4Runtime messages must be converted. These identifiers specify which table, counter, or other entity to retrieve information from, or, in the case of a write operation (i.e., inserting a match-action entry), the identifier of the action to be performed. The entire message must be traversed to ensure that all fields are accurately transformed. An inverse transformation is applied to response messages received from the data plane nodes, restoring identifiers to the format expected by the NF control plane.

In addition to handling such transformations, the proxy maintains the current state of all data plane objects based on the incoming P4Runtime messages from NF-CPs. This ensures that in the event of a rearrangement or restart, the state can be rebuilt independently of the NF-CPs, as such operations are designed to remain hidden from it. To achieve this, the proxy connects to a Redis server, leveraging its high-speed read/write capabilities to store state data, implementing a persistency layer. Upon receiving a message, the proxy updates Redis with the corresponding entries.

For restoration, a replay-based method is employed in the current implementation. This approach involves storing messages that create new entries and modifying messages that update existing entries in Redis. When a node requires reconfiguration, the proxy replays the stored messages to rebuild its state seamlessly.

5.2.3 Usage and Interfaces

The proxy can be configured via a JSON file. In this file, you can specify mappings that configure the operation of the proxy. A mapping specifies how messages should be routed and transformed. The source determines what will be visible to the control plane. The target specifies the structure of the data plane layer.

In case of aggregation, we specify multiple sources and one target. In case of disaggregation, one source and multiple targets need to be defined. For the sources and targets, we must also specify the p4 programs so that the data plane initialization and the transformation of the messages are possible.

In the case of aggregation, we also specify a prefix for the sources, with which we specify what prefix the entity names will have in the consolidated P4 file, so we can avoid name conflicts in the case of the aggregated P4 file.

In the case of disaggregation, we also need to define a name mapping, which table/counter, etc. to which data plane it was allocated and with what name during the disaggregation of the P4 program.

One of the most basic example configurations that combines two functions on one node is shown below. The table name `ipv4_lpm` in the `function1.p4` (we will call this as program `function1`) file should appear as `NF1_ipv4_lpm` in the `aggregated.p4` file. Note that the proxy follows the naming convention used in the P4 data plane aggregator component described in Section 5.3.

An example for this configuration:

```
{
  "redis": "READWRITE",
  "mappings": [
    {
      "target": {
        "program_name": "aggregated",
        "port": 50051,
        "device_id": 0
      },
      "sources": [
        {
          "program_name": "function1",
          "prefix": "NF1_",
          "controller_port": 60051
        },
        {
          "program_name": "function2",
          "prefix": "NF2_",
          "controller_port": 60052
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

When the proxy receives a table entry from a controller, such as the controller of the function1 program targeting the ipv4_lpm table, it processes a unique key within the message that identifies the table. This identifier is resolved by the proxy using the p4info file generated from the source function1.p4 file. The table, identified as MyIngress.ipv4_lpm, is then prefixed by the proxy to create a new name, such as MyIngress.NF1_ipv4_lpm. This prefixed name is subsequently converted into a corresponding identifier using the aggregated.p4info file.

The same transformation process is applied to the actions associated with the table entries. Using the new identifiers derived through this process, the proxy generates a modified message, which is then sent to the node running the aggregated P4 program.

Additionally, the proxy can function as a library, allowing direct implementation of the proxy class by specifying parameters through the JSON configuration.

5.2.4 Evaluation

The current version of the proxy introduces some processing overhead, which reduces the maximum achievable P4Runtime message throughput. Our evaluation only focused on write messages (e.g., inserting entries into a match-action table). In our initial tests, sending P4Runtime messages directly in the test environment achieves approximately 2,500 messages per second (baseline scenario). When using the proxy, with either aggregation or disaggregation, this rate decreases to 1,500 messages per second. However, this throughput still significantly exceeds the requirements of most typical scenarios. When multiple write updates are bundled into a single message, the throughput decreases in both the proxy and baseline cases. However, in scenarios requiring a large number of updates, batching them together allows the proxy to handle up to approximately 30,000 updates per second, thereby significantly improving maximum throughput in such cases. IML Control Plane proxy has been implemented in Python and the main bottleneck seems to be the Python-based gRPC library.

5.2.5 Limitations and further plans

The proxy was implemented in Python using the standard gRPC library that proved to be a bottleneck limiting the achievable message rate. We have started investigating how these limitations can be resolved by better configuration of the gRPC server or using multiple threads in the processing.

The proxy mediates between multiple NF-DP and NF-CP instances and is responsible for the isolation between them. However, such a component may be a potential target for attackers and needs to be secured and extended with authentication and authorization mechanisms to ensure trustworthiness and security. These aspects will be further analyzed in the next phase of the project.

5.3 P4 Data Plane Aggregator

The current P4 programmability model assumes that a P4 programmable device is owned and controlled by a single tenant. However, in typical NFV scenarios, support for multiple tenants is desirable. When each tenant may want to deploy its own P4 pipeline offering different network functions, supporting multiple co-existing tenant pipelines on a single platform is difficult because it requires pipeline merging, control plane support, and resource management of the platform. In DESIRE6G, we

developed a novel compiler-addons for automatic merging multiple P4-pipelines. This meta-compiler we call P4-MTAGG combines multiple P4-pipelines while preserving individual functionality and injecting additional functionality into the aggregated pipeline for packet classification, resource management and monitoring. The meta-compiler i) merges individual parsers into a single one capable to parse packets as defined in all source pipelines, ii) combines the match-action stages from all pipelines, dealing with possible naming collisions and iii) adds additional tables and parser states to identify incoming packets based on control headers (DESIRE6G or SRv6 header) and the NF IDs provided in the configuration and apply the correct NF, collect statistics about per tenant NF packet processing rates and resource (e.g., bandwidth, memory) usage and apply rate-limiting to each NF as configured by the proxy defined in Section 5.2. We note that currently the meta-compiler supports two control header types: i) DESIRE6G header where the NF identification is based on the nextNF field, 2) SRv6 where the segment ID is used to determine the NF pipeline to be executed.

5.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Supporting multiple tenants in a single programmable target poses multiple challenges, including i) how to merge the individual tenants' NFs so that they can be deployed on the target (as the target typically has less pipelines than number of NFs of all tenants that should be deployed), ii) how to provide control plane access to individual tenants, as the merged NFs typically only expose a single control plane interface that all tenants must share and iii) how to manage the target resources between tenants, such as memory (e.g., TCAM entries, SRAM) processing power (e.g., processed packets per second) or control plane load (e.g., number of installed/updated rules per second).

Some recent works tackled similar issues. For example, μ P4 [16] proposes a novel programming language/framework based on the P4-standard that focuses on modularity and interoperability of different functions. However, support of different tenants is not provided. Our framework allows for modularity without deviating from the P4-16 standard, significantly enhancing interoperability with other projects based on the standard. Placement of NFs and its impact on performance and resource consumption has been discussed in [17]. While it assumes that a host is capable of deploying multiple NFs, the process to support this has not been solved. Supporting multiple tenants on a single platform with implications on the control interface has been discussed in [18], but is limited to fixed-function

multi-tenancy. Lemur [19] allows to merge multiple NFs but does not consider multiple tenants and resource sharing policies between the different NFs.

5.3.2 Implementation

The P4-MTAGG compiler extension is based on the T4P4S [5] compiler developed by ELTE, utilizing its high-level intermediate representation module HLR for internal P4-representation and manipulation. The compiler extension takes multiple P4 files as input and outputs a single P4 file of the aggregated pipeline as well as corresponding P4Runtime-information for use in the control plane proxy.

FIGURE 16: OVERVIEW OF THE P4-MTAGG META-COMPILER

Figure 16 shows the different steps of the code aggregation process. HLR is a Python library to generate a program graph with all the object defined in the P4 code. The meta-compiler then applies different code transformations on the input HLIRs:

1. Parser and header merging: P4-parsers can be described as a graph, with the states being graph nodes and the select statements defining transitions. The merge process must find a new parser graph that functionally unionizes the individual parser graphs. Packets that are accepted by at least one input parser should be accepted by the resulting aggregated parser. We developed an algorithm that merges both parser-graphs into a single, logically unified graph. The strategy removes redundant states where applicable but preserves the different functionality of both graphs where applicable. Additionally, a strategy for identifying if a packet would have been accepted by one or the other input P4 program is introduced.
2. Control block merging: The second major building blocks of a P4-pipeline are control blocks. The number and kind of control blocks are defined by the P4 architecture. In a typical scenario (e.g.,

P4-Portable Switch Architecture) there are four control blocks, being grouped into in- and egress pipelines. Both pipelines start with a parser, then a match-action control block follows and they end with a deparser which reassembles the packet. Between the in- and egress pipelines, packets are typically buffered and can be replicated or cloned. Aggregating a P4-pipeline also requires aggregating all architecture-defined control blocks. This task can be split for the two "kinds" of control blocks encountered in a pipeline, match-action blocks and deparser blocks. Together with the already aggregated parsers these three types of blocks form all available high-level constructs in P4. To keep the input pipelines isolated in the data plane, we do not merge tables of individual pipelines even though their internal structure is the same. The merging process also consider that some header names, field names or variable names may be changed after aggregation and modify the references accordingly (e.g., the same variable name is used in two P4 programs to be aggregated).

3. Renaming data plane objects: Names of control blocks are used in the P4-runtime to set the target of control commands. When two pipelines are merged, these names might collide. In the program itself, naming separation can easily be achieved by some pre- or postfix on colliding names. On the control plane, a clearer distinction between pipelines is necessary. The same goes for counters. Custom counters must be added to the program that correctly count the packets on either pipeline, on a global as well as per table-basis. To expose all control elements in a concise way to the control plane, an additional proxy is necessary, that translates between the original naming in the source pipelines and the names in the merged pipeline on the target.
4. Deparser merging: The purpose of the deparser block is to reassemble the packet before leaving the pipeline or the device altogether. Their main purpose is reattaching the necessary headers for the packet in the correct order. We implemented a method ensuring that 1) resulting deparsing block contains one emit statement for every header emitted in at least one of the input deparsing blocks; 2) the relative order of emit statements from both input blocks is not changed; 3) the relative order of emit statements of not-similar headers to similar (and merged) headers is not modified.
5. Introduction of additional code blocks: The meta-compiler also extends the original pipeline with additional control elements. First, the parser is extended with a control header parsing state. The

control header could be either a DESIRE6G header or a SRv6 header. This header carries the network function identifier used to select the pipeline to be executed by the P4 target. This selection is based on a classification match-action table. To monitor the load of the different NFs, the pipeline is extended with statistics collection components at both ingress and egress. Sharing the resources between the deployed NFs and tenants is controlled by a meter-based rate limiter deployed at ingress before the pipeline execution. In this way, we can differentiate between the deployed data plane pipelines according to their importance.

The transformations merge the input HLRs into a single HLR program graph. As a final step, the meta-compiler generates the P4 code from the aggregated HLR and creates a configuration file for the P4Runtime Proxy. This configuration includes the mapping between the data plane objects in the individual P4 programs and the aggregated program after renaming, the identifier of NFs the aggregated program contains. The resulting P4 pipeline is depicted in Figure 17.

FIGURE 17: OVERVIEW OF THE AGGREGATED PIPELINE

The P4-MTAGG meta-compiler has been implemented in Python and relies on the T4P4S P4 compiler.

5.3.3 Usage and Interfaces

The P4-MTAGG compiler can either be used as a command line tool or as a Python library. An orchestrator component has also been developed to automate the aggregation, deployment and control plane proxy configuration processes.

5.3.4 Evaluation

Our initial evaluation [14][15] focuses on the impact of deploying NFs in an aggregated environment by answering the following research questions: 1) What is the overhead of our aggregation approach? 2)

How does mixing traffic loads between two aggregated pipelines impact latency and throughput? 3)
How can fairness between NFs be evaluated?

The testbed setup consists of two servers: one equipped with a Netronome Agilio smartNIC 2x40G that executes the aggregated P4 program and another traffic generator node running Cisco T-Rex. The two nodes are interconnected with two 40Gbps links. All tests aim to find the maximal achievable non-drop rate (NDR) with 60 second iterations and are repeated 10 times. Packet size was 128 bytes. We created 3 different NFs with various complexity as summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1: NF PIPELINES WITH DIFFERENT COMPLEXITY

	NF1	NF2	NF3
#parsed headers	0	5	10
#tables	1	6	11
#hash calculations	0	1	5

FIGURE 18: INDIVIDUAL P4 PIPELINE PERFORMANCE (BARS REPRESENT NDR, LATENCY IS MARKED WITH RED HORIZONTAL LINES)

Figure 18 shows that performance significantly deteriorates when we run more complex (more tables, more complex parsers) P4-pipelines on the smartNIC. In addition, the performance of aggregated pipelines is worse than using the non-aggregated ones due to the additional parsing of header, tables and meters due to our synthesized code for managing pertinent fairness. Observed latency increases

are in line with performance differences, with a higher relative increase in latency for functions with lower individual latencies.

FIGURE 19: MIXED TRAFFIC IN AGGREGATED PIPELINES

Figure 19 shows that when mixing traffic between two pipelines of different complexity the reached NDR changes linearly between the individual (aggregated) NF NDRs. Latency is also lower for the NF with less effort but is affected by traffic mix. The collected data also allows to calculate the fairness of a specific traffic mix. As a pure bandwidth-based fairness calculation does not represent the different efforts required to process a single packet in different NFs, the used bandwidth is based on cumulative packet handling time of the aggregated NFs ($\text{pps} \times \text{latency}$). This calculation yields peak fairness at 20/80 (NF1/NF3), 20/80 (NF1/NF2) and 40/60 (NF2/NF3).

5.3.5 Limitations and further plans

We currently work on porting the solution to Tofino target. The TNA architecture support has already been added to the HLIR of T4P4S compiler that is used by the P4-MTAGG metacompiler. Extending the solution to new P4 hardware may require the extension of the HLIR with the architecture support. Currently available P4 hardware targets do not support the change of the P4 program without interrupting the operation. This may change in the future. Currently this limitation can be bypassed if a spare instance of the same hardware is used and in case of update the spare hardware takes over the role of the old hardware instance with the new P4 program. After that the old instance becomes the spare device.

6 Performance isolation for supporting deep slicing

As broadband access speeds continue to increase across both mobile and fixed networks, new and pressing challenges are emerging in the Access-Aggregation Network (AAN), which plays a critical role in delivering high-speed data services to end users. While advances in access technologies have driven impressive growth in last-mile speeds, they have inadvertently shifted bottlenecks to the AAN itself. This trend threatens to undermine the full benefits of broadband access if transmission constraints within the AAN are not addressed with effective scalability and isolation mechanisms. Performance isolation ensures that the congestion level and resources utilized by a slice do not negatively affect the performance of another [22]. Moreover, within a slice, when high-speed links are shared among thousands, or even millions, of subscribers without right performance isolation, competition for bandwidth increases, especially during peak traffic times. In such cases, the resource sharing depends largely on the number of active flows each subscriber has, and the specific congestion control mechanisms employed. This lack of control over how resources are shared among subscribers can lead to an unpredictable and often unfair distribution of bandwidth, degrading user experience and limiting the quality of service for latency-sensitive applications such as streaming, gaming, and real-time communication.

Scheduling and Active Queue Management (AQM) are critical for ensuring performance isolation, as they directly influence how resources are allocated and managed among different slices, as well as within each slice between users, since scheduling ensures appropriate and efficient allocation of network resources, while AQM manages congestion and queue performance. However, traffic management in current switches is rigid, supporting only a limited set of predefined algorithms. Thus, operators are restricted to reconfiguring algorithm parameters without the ability to modify the underlying algorithm logic. While numerous algorithms have been developed for various network scenarios, fixed packet scheduling and complementary AQM schemes struggle to adapt to the complexities of network environments, especially looking into the intricacies and hard requirements of mobile network traffic. The ability to program the data plane offers a unique opportunity for implementing flexible and customizable traffic management within and across network slices. An extensive list of programmable scheduling and AQM approaches is provided in [20].

6.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

With regards to the scheduling approach, adopting traditional fairness mechanisms, such as Fair Queueing (FQ) scheduling [25], are theoretically capable of enforcing equal (or weighted) resource distribution across users. However, these methods struggle to scale effectively as the number of subscribers grows, due to the impracticality of maintaining large number of queues, and processing flows individually. As broadband access expands to support dense urban populations and remote regions alike, a scalable solution that can isolate performance effectively at high user counts is becoming essential. Implementing weighted fairness for 1 million users is challenging due to many factors: 1) it requires significant resource constraints on network hardware, such as limited memory and processing power, which makes it difficult to track and manage per-user state at high speeds. 2) Ensuring fair queueing requires many queues or complex scheduling algorithms that do not scale well, especially as traffic demands shift dynamically and require real-time adjustments. 3) These fairness mechanisms may increase latency and computational load, which can disrupt high-throughput, low-latency applications. Solutions often involve trade-offs, like grouping users or using approximate methods, to balance scalability with practical performance. Looking into performance isolation between different network slices, authors in [21] employ a customizable AQM-driven virtual queue per slice to meet their bandwidth allocation and delay demands. Virtual queue-based traffic management schemes (e.g., AQM [23], scheduling [24], etc.) have been widely employed for legacy switching devices. The programmable traffic management approach described in [22] has been employed for a packet-based, software-defined transport network, demonstrating the efficiency of the approach for 5G network slices.

In D4.1 (Section 3.2.1 of [1]) we advocated the use of virtual queues (slice-level) and rank/value-based (UE level) methods for HQoS resource sharing policies. To this end we designed and implemented a scalable, data plane-based packet marker method for the core-stateless resource sharing scheduler called CSAQM [21][22], specifically implemented for the Tofino ASIC. We show that the packet marker running on a single Tofino switch can mark the traffic of over one million users at line rate, indicating a substantial leap forward in scalable, fair resource allocation within the AAN. We also extended the packet marker with a simple, yet flexible policy configuration interface to support the adaptation of the HQoS policies via the IML. At the same time, we are currently adapting the inter-slice performance

isolation approach using virtual queues [22] to the TNA architecture of the Tofino ASIC. So far, this approach has only been implemented and tested on software switch BMV2 and SmartNIC (Netronome Agilio) platforms [21]. The adaptation process involves redesigning the pipeline, as Tofino's architecture imposes strict limitations on conditional branching, stateful operations, and sequential dependencies within a single pipeline stage. These constraints make it challenging to implement the complex logic and multiple stateful variable updates required for the per-slice AQM approach, which will be detailed in the deliverable D4.3, along with the integration and interoperability with the Per Packet Value (PPV) framework [26][27][28].

6.2 Performance isolation within a slice

For performance isolation within a slice we apply the Per Packet Value (PPV) framework [26][27][28]. The PPV method relies on the core-stateless resource sharing principle, using two key elements:

- **a packet marker** which assigns values to each packet of a user (or more generally a traffic aggregate) according to a predefined resource sharing policy; and
- **a scheduler and Active Queue Management (AQM)**, which uses the values carried by packets to decide whether to drop a packet or mark it with ECN Congestion Encountered (CE) flag if the buffer is getting full.

Each traffic aggregate (e.g., UE generated traffic) within a slice can be marked with PVs independently. The marker labels incoming packets with a drop precedence level known as the Packet Value (PV). This marking process is stateful because it depends on the throughput of the traffic aggregate and the specific resource-sharing policy defined by a policy function called Throughput-Value Function (TVF). Each packet marker operates independently of other markers, network topology, and current network conditions.

The scheduler is deployed at each node (e.g., routers, end-hosts) within the PPV domain, as any node can potentially become a bottleneck. During periods of congestion, these nodes prioritize packets by PV, dropping or marking packets with the smallest PVs first, rather than using traditional methods like dropping the last packet or dropping uniformly at random. Several studies have demonstrated efficient

algorithms and implementations of this PV-based scheduling on P4-programmable hardware. Our method in DESIRE6G relies on these implementations [26][28].

An essential part of implementing the framework is to tag packets with PVs, using a Throughput-Value Function (TVF), which is derived from a utility function. The utility function expresses the relationship between the allocated throughput and the user's satisfaction. The derivative of the utility function represents the extra value (e.g., the increase in the user's satisfaction) gained by providing an extra unit of throughput to the user.

Practically, the packet marker for each user measures the sending rate R , selects a rate x uniformly from the range $[0, R]$ when a packet arrives, and assigns a PV $p=V(x)$ to the packet where $V(\cdot)$ is the throughput-value function mapping rates to PVs. This results in a distribution of PVs for each traffic aggregate, enabling differentiated treatment in the network.

FIGURE 20: EXAMPLE THROUGHPUT-VALUE-FUNCTION (TVF) AND RESOURCE SHARING EXAMPLE WITH THE PPV FRAMEWORK

Figure 20 illustrates how the TVFs and PVs can be used to share the bottleneck capacity between various users. In the first case, the bottleneck capacity is 10 Mbps shared between three user flows. The red, blue and green curves on the right side represent the TVFs of Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. The gray dotted line illustrates the cutoff value that results in a resource allocation 0, 6.25 and 3.75Mbps for Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. This allocation is ensured by only transmitting packets with PV above the cutoff level. One can observe that Flow1 has no packet with PV above this threshold and thus it cannot even transmit a single packet. In the case of a 45Mbps bottleneck, the cutoff value is much smaller and thus

all three flows have non-zero assigned throughput. The purple dotted line represents the cutoff value, leading to 10, 17.5 and 17.5Mbps throughput allocation for Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. In this case, packets below the threshold marked by the purple line are only dropped (or marked with ECN CE).

Note that the PPV concept also supports HQoS policies but at the expense of higher computational complexity in the packet marker [28].

6.2.1 Implementation

In DESIRE6G, we improved the P4-based packet marker algorithm to become more scalable. As mentioned, for each traffic aggregate (u) the packet marker continuously monitors the arrival rate $R(u)$, selects a random sample uniformly between 0 and $R(u)$ and applies the user's TVF $v(u)$ at this sampled value to determine the packet value for tagging the packet. Although conceptually straightforward, implementing this mechanism on a P4-programmable ASIC like Tofino introduces challenges due to hardware constraints. For example, Tofino does not natively support floating-point arithmetic, cannot generate random numbers in arbitrary integer ranges, and imposes restrictions on multiplication operations. To overcome these limitations, we developed a streamlined packet marking algorithm specifically tailored to the Tofino ASIC, as illustrated in Figure 21.

FIGURE 21: P4 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PV MARKER

The packet processing pipeline begins with a subscriber classification step implemented by the SubscriberRate table. Note that in more general this table identifies the traffic aggregate the processed packet belongs to. This table matches each packet based on a subscriber (UE) identifier (e.g., IPv4/IPv6 address) and then executes an action that updates the corresponding rate measurement R and assign the appropriate resource-sharing policy identifier for the user’s traffic. The arrival rate for each user is calculated by updating a dedicated low-pass filter object with the packet size in Tofino’s data plane.

Due to the lack of support for direct multiplication of arbitrary variables, we employ a logarithmic transformation: taking the logarithm of both variables and summing them. Similarly to prior studies, we assume the TVF policy function exhibits exponential decay. This assumption allows us to use exponential binning of the throughput axis, yielding a discretized representation of the TVF. As shown in the figure, bin sizes are equidistant on a logarithmic scale. The bin Δ_i represents the throughput range from a^{i-1} to a^i for a predefined base value $1 < a < 2$. This table is precomputed, ensuring the upper bound of the final bin accommodates the maximum possible per-user rate. In our implementation, we

use 1024 bins. To store the packet value in a finite number of bits, each bin Δ_i is mapped to a discrete packet value level ($v(a^{i-1})$), represented by red lines in the figure.

To enable this compact representation, we first map the measured rate R to a bin index i , using the RateIndex table. This table applies range matching on the user's rate R and returns i such that $R \in \Delta_i$. Since the ASIC can only generate random values within the range $[0, 2^{n-1}]$ (for bit-width $n \geq 1$), we take a random value rnd from range 0 to 255 and then compute the logarithm of $\frac{rnd}{255}R$. The multiplication is then approximated by summing the logarithms of the two values. The RandomRateEstim table implements this logarithmic transformation and adjusts the bin index i accordingly, yielding a randomized index $rndbin$. As the logarithm of the random value is negative, its complement ($y(x)$) is computed and stored in the table. Overflow-protected subtraction, denoted as "I-I" in the figure, ensures the correct bin index is determined during table execution. The offset denoted by $y(x)$ is precomputed and embedded in the table.

Finally, the packet value for tagging is determined by applying the PolicyFunction table, which stores the discretized representations of various policy functions.

In addition to packet marking, the PPV framework also requires a specialized packet scheduler and AQM method. In DESIRE6G, we use the Tofino-based P4 implementation of CSAQM scheduler as presented in [26]. In addition to the P4 implementation, we also implemented a simple PPV scheduler as a Linux kernel module.

6.3 Usage and Interfaces

The scheduler operates autonomously without requiring further configuration or tuning once deployed. In contrast, the Packet Marking component requires specific configurations for each user and traffic aggregate. To streamline the configuration of the Per Packet Value (PPV) framework, we introduced a simple yet flexible policy definition interface within the IML. This interface allows users to define policies that are subsequently mapped to a throughput-value function in the Packet Marker component. The defined policies are loaded into the PolicyFunction table within the P4 program using P4Runtime or BFRT.

Each policy outlines one or more bandwidth segments, each with an associated weight. The structure of a policy is as follows:

- **Guaranteed Segment:** Defines a minimum bandwidth that the system guarantees. Includes a weight to determine how bandwidth is shared during congestion. If the guaranteed minimum cannot be met, intervention from the higher layer (e.g., SMO) is required to adjust routing or allocate additional resources. The weight becomes relevant only during congestion, ensuring proportional bandwidth sharing when the guaranteed minimum cannot be fulfilled for all traffic groups.
- **Best Effort Segments:** Activated only after the guaranteed segment's requirements are fully met for all flows sharing the same bottleneck. Each best effort segment is defined by: A bandwidth limit, representing the maximum bandwidth allocated to the segment. A weight, which determines bandwidth sharing in cases where the segment cannot be fully satisfied. Subsequent best effort segments are activated sequentially, only if the preceding segment's bandwidth limit is completely utilized. The last best effort segment includes a hard throughput limit, indicating the maximum allowable bandwidth for the traffic group.

During congestion, the guaranteed segment bandwidth is shared proportionally based on weights if the system cannot meet all minimum requirements. If the guaranteed segments are satisfied, best effort segments are activated progressively, ensuring fair bandwidth distribution according to their weights and limits. When there is surplus capacity, "higher-priority" best effort segments are satisfied first, followed by lower-priority segments as additional bandwidth becomes available.

Policies are expressed in a YAML format. Each policy includes: 1) A policy ID for unique identification, 2) A network service ID linking it to the associated service, 3) A traffic group ID specifying the traffic aggregate to which the policy applies, 4) Bandwidth segments with their respective limits and weights.

An example can be seen for such a policy configuration below:

```
policy:  
id: 2  
ns-id: 1  
traffic-group-id: 8472  
segments:  
- type: guaranteed  
min_bandwidth_kbps: 2000  
weight: 10  
- type: best_effort  
bandwidth_limit_kbps: 35000  
weight: 4  
- type: best_effort  
bandwidth_limit: 1000000  
weight: 1
```

This flexible policy configuration enables fine-grained control over bandwidth allocation and prioritization, ensuring that traffic aggregates can adapt dynamically to varying network conditions. The integration with P4Runtime and BFRT ensures efficient deployment of these policies into the programmable data plane, aligning with the unified data plane layer's goals in DESIRE6G.

6.4 Evaluation

6.4.1 PPV method with the scalable packet marker

Our evaluation setup is depicted in Figure 22. The setup includes four servers, represented as yellow boxes, which act as traffic sources and sinks. A single Tofino switch is utilized to perform both packet marking and CSAQM scheduling. Since our testbed includes only one Tofino switch, the two data plane pipelines are co-located on the same device. A 100 Gbps bottleneck link is created by interconnecting the Tofino switch with a non-programmable switch, and this bottleneck is managed by the CSAQM scheduler.

Thousands of UDP flows, simulating subscriber traffic, are generated using the DPDK PktGen tool on TrafficGen-2, which connects to the Tofino switch via two 100 Gbps links. The throughput of these flows is monitored using a DPDK-based collector program running on TrafficSink-2, connected via a single 100 Gbps link. The other source and sink machines, TrafficGen-1 and TrafficSink-1, run iperf2 to generate traffic for designated subscribers, with each connected via a 40 Gbps link.

Measurements are collected from both sink nodes and the P4 switch. Each user is assigned either a Silver or Gold policy, configured to achieve a throughput sharing ratio of 1:3.4 between Silver and Gold users, respectively.

FIGURE 22: TESTBED SETUP

FIGURE 23: P4 MARKER WITH 8000 SILVER UDP FLOWS,
2000 GOLD UDP FLOWS, 10 CUBIC TCP BACKGROUND
AND 2 DESIGNATED UDP 15MBPS AND 50MBPS FLOWS

Figure 23 illustrates a scenario with 8000 Silver users, 2000 Gold users, and two designated Gold UDP flows (representing two designated users). The traffic for Silver and Gold users is generated by two separate interfaces of the machine TrafficGen-2, with Silver users on one interface and Gold users on the other. This setup produces a total load of 200Gbps on the bottleneck link.

The applied policies yield average per-user throughputs of 21.8Mbps and 6.4Mbps for the Gold and Silver classes, respectively. It is depicted on the top subfigure. The throughput variation is insignificant. The designated users, governed by the Gold policy, generate traffic from TrafficGen-1. One flow transmits at 15Mbps, starting at 24 seconds (denoted as t_1), while the other begins at 50 seconds (t_2) and transmits at 50Mbps.

The bottom subfigure depicts the loss rates experienced by the two designated users. The first user, with a sending rate below its fair share of 21.8Mbps, incurs no packet loss. In contrast, the second user, transmitting at a rate higher than its fair share (50Mbps), experiences a 58% loss. Notably, despite the high loss, the second user achieves the same throughput as other Gold users.

This scenario demonstrates the resource-sharing behavior of our packet marker and scheduler under conditions of high but stable traffic loads. It highlights that users demanding less than their fair share remain unaffected by the high loss rates of other subscribers. Different users may experience very different packet losses at the bottleneck.

The initial implementation of the proposed packet marker supports up to 35,800 users while utilizing 5 out of 12 available stages on Tofino hardware. The most resource-intensive component of this implementation is the SubscriberRate table, which consumes SRAM and MapRAM resources to perform user classification and rate measurements based on a Low-Pass Filter (LPF). Despite this complexity, the overall resource consumption remains modest, at 6.1% of SRAM and 6.6% of MapRAM, primarily due to the 66% and 75% utilization in the stage where SubscriberRate and rate measurement operations occur. Seven additional stages remain available in Tofino for other essential network functions, such as forwarding, routing, or User Plane Function (UPF) tasks.

To increase the number of users supported by a single packet marking device, we addressed the 35,800-user limit imposed by the per-stage capacity of LPF objects used for rate measurements. By creating multiple instances of the SubscriberRate table and corresponding LPF arrays, we ensured that each

instance handles a separate subset of users, distributing user-based rate measurements across multiple stages. Each additional stage dedicated to packet marking expands the capacity by another 35,800 users. With one stage reserved for packet forwarding, the maximum user capacity in a single Tofino pipeline reaches 250,250. The overall utilization of mostly used resources still remains modest, at 63.1% of SRAM and 44.1% of MapRAM. Tofino switches have either 2 or 4 pipelines, which run data plane programs independently over different port ranges. One can observe that the number of users supported can exceed 1 million when each pipeline is configured to manage a distinct set of traffic aggregates.

6.5 Limitations and further plans

The main limitation of the PPV contribution is the missing place of the Packet value in a header. The Desire6G has own header that can store this value. The proposed solution works within the Desire6G network. Transport network needs also implement PPV-based traffic management. We work on a method that solves this problem by mapping the packet values to DSCP drop precedence level according to an offline throughput allocation method. In this case the switches can handle the packet with a DSCP-aware AQM like RED/WRED with different profiles for the different DSCP values that is supported by most non-programmable switches.

7 Components in the pervasive monitoring framework

Pervasive intelligence, automated management and (near) real-time control call for an equally pervasive and real-time monitoring system. However, monitoring has been so far applied without providing a comprehensive framework with global visibility on all resources, efficiently supporting scalable network management and control at different timescales. The DESIRE6G system leverages on the concept of pervasive data-driven monitoring to support zero-touch control, management, and orchestration. Monitoring data can originate from either service elements, adhering to the DESIRE6G definition of the E2E service or the infrastructure. This section describes different components implementing various data collection and monitoring methods including in-band network telemetry, telemetry collection, telemetry agent.

7.1 MAS Telemetry agent

The distributed system consists of several interconnected software components. Specifically, the *MAS telemetry agent*, which is part of the distributed telemetry architecture, includes:

- a telemetry collector that periodically receives telemetry data from the P4 collector;
- a per-flow telemetry processor.

The role of these telemetry components is to compute the required measurements and statistics that characterize the current QoS of the traffic flow, from the received INT telemetry.

7.1.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The MAS telemetry is part of the MAS distributed intelligence proposed by DESIRE6G for near-real-time autonomous service operation, which is a special type of network automation that requires the availability of new technologies and architectures to be developed in the control and data planes to perform decisions in the seconds timescale.

7.1.2 Implementation

The architecture of the agents is based on the UPC GODAI platform, which consists of five main components: *i*) a *manager* module configuring and supervising the operation of the rest of the modules; *ii*) a *security manager* in charge of security aspects, like key management; *iii*) a number of *algorithms* for data processing that include data processing and intelligence; *iv*) a number of *interfaces* to communicate with other systems. Additionally, interfaces take care of the security of telemetry data, e.g., to ensure data privacy, authentication, and integrity; and *v*) a *Redis DB* that is used in *publish-subscribe* (pub/sub) mode by the different modules to communicate with each other, i.e., no direct communication is allowed. This facilitates the definition of specific workflows for telemetry data and provides an agile, reliable, and secure environment that simplifies communication, as well as integration of new modules.

The realization of the MAS agents includes the development of (see Figure 24):

- *Telemetry adaptors* to collect measurements from other systems, like P4 switches, and to adapt the data to the internal structure of the agent.
- *Telemetry collector* that processes the measurements and separates them for each of the flows.
- *Flow Telemetry processor* that aggregates the received measurements and generates periodical reports for the agents in the MAS.
- *Intelligent agent* that includes the MAS intelligence.
- MAS interface to communicate with other agents in the MAS and with the MAS supervisor in the MLFO.
- Control interfaces to communicate to other control systems in the DESIRE6G architecture, including the SDNC, IML, etc.

FIGURE 24: ARCHITECTURE OF THE AGENTS

7.1.3 Usage and Interfaces

The interfaces of the MAS telemetry agent are REST-based. Specifically, the telemetry adaptor retrieves the following measurements:

Traffic telemetry for every monitored flow:

- Flow Id
- List of metrics and measured values during the specified period

E2e telemetry for every monitored flow:

- Flow Id

- List of metrics and aggregated values (delay, jitter and load in our case) during the specified period disaggregated by route.

VXLANs are used for near real-time communication among the agents (MAS interface). VXLAN allows creating an overlay over a physical network to provide a service abstraction layer in virtualized environments. This solution provides quick set up and enables creating millions of networks in parallel (simultaneous segments). At the same time, VXLAN presents some security concerns, such as the possibility for *rogue devices* to join one or more multicast groups and inject fake traffic. Encryption protocols, such as IPsec, encrypt both the content and the inner headers, which reduces rogue risk, as compared to other real-time encryption protocols at the application level.

In addition, to reduce the delay added for encryption and to allow other MAS agents to verify and trace communications, in our implementation we use pre-shared secrets. Then, such solution needs from an authentication infrastructure for authorized agents to obtain and distribute such secrets. We rely on DLT for that purpose. In particular, the security intrinsic features of DLTs can be used to, once the association between agents is agreed, securely manage VXLANs as communication channels among the agents. Note that the impact of the consensus mechanism used is limited to the set-up phase of the dynamic associations between agents and does not have an impact on the actual exchanges between them once the associations are established.

7.1.4 Evaluation

The telemetry agent has been integrated with the P4 collector and used for several demonstrations [29][30].

We have evaluated the computation time required by the agent making decisions, as this is paramount for scalability and reactivity. Note that the designed system includes two elements that might require long computation time: *i*) the REDIS DB in pub/sub mode as the central system supporting the communication among the different components; and *ii*) the intelligent algorithms, which are based on deep reinforcement learning (DRL), so it has to evaluate complex neural networks to produce the resulting action. The total mean (max) running time for decision making is 26 (29) ms., which includes 1.5

ms of added delay to every message exchanged through the REDIS DB, and 20 ms for the DRL-based algorithm. Hence, the designed system shows high effectiveness, and it can support near-real time control of network services.

7.1.5 Limitations and further plans

Currently, telemetry adaptors and processors have been developed to receive measurements from P4 collectors. Additional adaptors and processors need to be developed for different telemetry data sources.

7.2 Telemetry collector and in-network control

As network technologies evolve, operators increasingly require ubiquitous network intelligence to support comprehensive network automation, across different timescales, in order to cope with the scale of operations, and meet stringent Service Level Agreements (SLAs). This in turn, necessitates an equally pervasive monitoring system. According to the IETF, Network telemetry is a technology for gaining network insight and facilitating efficient and automated network management.

With the development of programmable data planes in-band Network Telemetry (INT) emerged, providing significant advantages, such as flexible programming, real-time and in-depth network visibility. This is being accomplished by inserting network state information directly into the data packet headers. Thus, the network measurement process is now being managed by the data plane without requiring intervention by the control plane. However, the P4 data plane framework for INT and other existing frameworks yield substantial transmission overhead, which grows linearly with the number of hops, as well as with the number of telemetry variables. Per-flow Aggregation (PFA) entails a lightweight form of INT, where the telemetry values are spread across the packets of a single flow, instead of compounding all the telemetry values in a single packet.

7.2.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The rapid collection of metadata statistics is necessary, but not sufficient to trigger a fast, real-time local-loop network intervention in the case of SLA violation. In the context of latency-sensitive services, end-

to-end latency exceeding a certain threshold due to network congestion may be detrimental and difficult to manage. In addition, considering emerging services such as distributed/federated learning, when highly bursty traffic is experienced, frequent short-time congestions may occur, thus implying, besides latency violations, packet loss and retransmissions, ultimately leading to significant service disruptions and delays. Such micro congestions, with a duration in the order of tens of microseconds, cannot be recovered relying on network agents at the control/management plane, due to the time needed to process telemetry data at higher layers. In fact, near real-time re-optimizations have been demonstrated to be effective in the tens-hundreds milliseconds duration timescale.

Motivated by the need for faster control loops for network automation, we demonstrate a new proposition that entails in-network control and monitoring of traffic flows using INT. Our solution enables rapid network reaction times through decisions taken at the data plane. Specifically, we show flexible and dynamic flow steering through the network, enabled by (i) ultra-fast identification of changes in the network state, in terms of detection of incipient congestion or degradation in the trustworthiness of the flow path, and (ii) exchanging control messages through the in-network communication channel, allowing the network to react immediately and steer the traffic flows via alternative (trust- and QoS-equivalent) routes, with no CPU involvement. The approach aims to significantly reduce reaction times by the infrastructure elements and improve the accuracy of measurements.

7.2.2 Implementation

Figure 25 provides an overview of the network topology and the loosely coupled set of components that constitute the proposed framework. The main parts of our proposed solution can be summarized in the following points:

- **Pervasive Telemetry.** It allows network elements to report metrics with a per-packet rate. We utilize the INT approach on a fully P4-programmable data-plane. The metadata are appended to the traffic, conveying crucial service metrics to a collection point.
- **Telemetry Collector.** The telemetry data is sent to the Telemetry Collector, a P4-programmable switch that performs in-network aggregation at wire speed. The Telemetry Collector is

responsible for the collection, aggregation, filtering, and correlation of the data. In essence it facilitates:

- the real-time identification of bottlenecks or unsolicited changes in the trust level of the flow path;
 - real-time or near real-time control loops, utilizing predefined control policies installed in the switch, or by feeding information to the controller, which dynamically makes decisions for near real-time closed loop operations. In this demo, we show case the former.
- **Telemetry Server.** The telemetry information is being forwarded from the collector switch to a telemetry server embedded into layer 2 data packets. Then the data are extracted and stored into a database.
 - **Dashboard.** The gathered telemetry information is displayed through a graphical user interface called (Dashboard) that provides:
 - the Topology section which is a topology graph that indicates in real-time the state of the user data flows, and all elements in the network via aggregated information;
 - the Monitoring section that displays the collected telemetry in real-time with statistical analysis tools;
 - an Information section with further instructions and assistance on how to operate the software.

FIGURE 25: NETWORK TOPOLOGY FOR INT

7.2.3 Usage and Interfaces

The structure of the Telemetry Headers is depicted in Figure 26. Telemetry data such as the Path Tracing and Trust related information is embedded to the packet as TCP Options, while an additional Congestion header is added after in the following.

FIGURE 26: TELEMETRY HEADER STRUCTURE

Similarly, the header structure of the INT-triggered control message, consists of the target Switch ID, the Port ID, along with flow identification metadata, for redirecting the flow to the desired path.

7.2.4 Evaluation

We are collecting different types of performance, security and routing metrics. The information is being embedded into the data packets either using PFA INT or traditional INT (embedding metadata on each hop) based on the type of metric. These include:

- 1) Path Tracing: The path is traced using unique identifiers for every switch along the path. This approach ensures that the user is aware of the path that is being used at any given time. The information is collected using Probabilistic PFA.
- 2) Trust: The trustworthiness of a path is calculated as the minimum trust of the nodes participating in the path. Each node is assigned a trust level based on several device-specific metrics, such as geo-location, running firmware, operator, interactions with other nodes, and similar criteria.
- 3) Congestion: The congestion level is being evaluated based on device-specific metadata which are available by the switches. Those are the queue length and the queue delay. The former one refers to the length of the buffer that temporarily stores the packets into the switch. The latter

is the delay that it takes for a single packet to go through that buffer. The congestion information is being gathered by using traditional INT. This way, no reconstruction of the telemetry data is needed, so that the congestion of the path is identified as soon as possible.

The experimental environment is the ARNO Testbed and it is co-hosted by CNIT and Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna in Pisa, Italy. The testbed includes several x86 servers that run network functions, service agents, applications, and emulated programmable network switches.

A commercial packet router and a pair of commercial OTN optical transport ROADMs, encompassing muxponder cards at 100G with coherent DSP and Ethernet tributaries at 10Gb/s, are deployed to exploit tight scheduling effects and multi-layer communication.

The probing traffic is generated with a Spirent N4U traffic generator/analyzer, with a pair of Ethernet interfaces at 10GB/s, injecting and receiving traffic with specific characteristics.

The programmable switches are running the Nikss software, providing an efficient implementation of fully configurable P4 switches, able to transmit the packets at wire speed. The switches run on general-purpose CPUs. Therefore, each switch operates on a dedicated server to achieve maximum efficiency.

We assume a client-server application scenario where the server is sending TCP traffic to the client through the programmable data-plane. As the data packets are traversing through the network, the switches are embedding telemetry data into the packet headers, employing either traditional INT or lightweight INT with PFA, depending on the measured metric. Once the traffic flow packets reach the last node in the path, the telemetry data are being extracted and sent to the telemetry collector, while traffic is forwarded as expected to the end-user.

We use a P4-programmable switch as telemetry collector to facilitate ultra-fast identification of bottlenecks or unsolicited changes in the trust level of the flow path. The telemetry collector retrieves and processes telemetry data for each traffic flow, such as the buffer size for each switch in the flow path, the trust level of the path along with path tracing info. The collector uses this information to:

1. Trigger the network to take action in case of service degradation, and
2. 2) Inform the telemetry collector about the state of the network, performing necessary computations and processing of the data at wire-speed.

The real-time QoS and trust properties of the active path are depicted in the Dashboard, as retrieved by the proposed framework, via the telemetry server. These include the real-time representation of the achieved QoS, color-coded as green, yellow, or red, depending in the level of congestion, and the trust level for all switches in the path indicated by color-coded nodes.

Scenario I: QoS Degradation. In the first scenario, we introduce background traffic in the packet router that will eventually lead to congestion in the data path. Specifically, we are causing congestion by sending multiple flows of 130 Mbps. We can observe via the Dashboard that the queue length increases in the switch P41 1 - that indicates a bottleneck, and the active path colour is changing in the Topology Explorer graph 2. Once congestion is detected by the collector using predefined thresholds for metrics such as queue size or delay as an indicator of anticipated SLA violation, the telemetry collector will request network service adaptation. This is achieved through sending the INT-triggered control message with Steering Flag ON in the reverse path, prompting the use of the optical bypass switches O1 and O2, which is the pre-defined backup path that adheres to the QoS and Trust requirements of the flow. The change of the path is then visible through the Dashboard, reflecting also the real-time QoS properties.

Scenario II: Trust Degradation (Interactive). In the second scenario, the attendee selects a switch along the active path whose trust level is reduced through the Command Line Interface, emulating the adaptation in the trustworthiness of the node caused e.g., by a change in its firmware, etc. We can observe through the Topology section of the Dashboard, that the trust level indicator colour changes for the specific switch according to the scale. Once the degradation in the trust level of the data path is detected, the telemetry collector will request network service adaptation, in a similar fashion as described or the previous scenario. As a result, the traffic is steered to the optical backup path that adheres to the trust requirements of the flow. All events will be visible through the Dashboard, reflecting the trustworthiness of the new active path.

7.3 P4 In-band Network Telemetry on UE

The P4-UE node encompasses mobility functionalities and programmable forwarding through an internal P4 switch (P4S).

Main information:

- Managing geo-localization and radio channel information through GPS receiver and radio modules.
- Ensuring forwarding of traffic through the network exploiting radio interface(s).
- Implementing the INT solution by adding additional metadata at the packet level of the data flow.

The P4-UE is implemented as a white box. The central P4S is connected through internal logical interfaces (Ix) to all the radio interface of the UE (px). It supports Ethernet-based interfaces. In the cases where different types of interfaces are available (e.g., non-Ethernet), an overlay mechanism based on VXLAN is adopted.

The different sensors of the node, for example, the CPU load level c, the geolocation tracking g and the radio link level r, provide their data to the Exporter API. The Exporter manages the incoming sensor data and writes their updated values inside specific P4 registers, resorting to the P4 switch command line interface.

The packets of the flows carrying payload are received by the P4S through I interfaces and are then processed. If matched, they are augmented with local INT header, including standard INT metadata (e.g., timestamps, hop latency) and specific INT metadata tc, tg and tr read from the P4S local registers.

7.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Implementing an extended In-Band Network Telemetry (INT) to collect state information on UE node, its actual properties and additional metadata. The extended telemetry includes non-standard P4 metadata such as the load of the CPU, its coordinates in the 3-dimensional space and the RSSI of the radio link.

7.3.2 Implementation

Extending the pervasive monitoring functionalities at the UE enables the operation even when network conditions change rapidly. A UE needs to be monitored periodically to ensure their functioning, detect relevant problems and apply network optimization.

Today, different types of network monitoring exist, including traffic probing and network equipment polling. Both of these approaches yield additional traffic that needs to travel over the network and are prone to performance issues.

In-Band Network Telemetry (INT) is an example of passive monitoring where monitoring information is directly appended to the data packets by each node along the path, instead of being sent in dedicated packets and without requiring intervention by the control plane.

The network state is obtained at the precise moment the real user traffic passes through, reflecting the instantaneous network performance and the exact treatment that an application packet undergoes. INT provides real-time insights, facilitating proactive issue detection and enabling the identification and addressing of potential problems before they escalate.

FIGURE 27: PACKET STRUCTURE

A dedicated In-band Telemetry (INT), leveraging the standard design of INT over UDP outlined is developed and implemented. Figure 27 shows the telemetry structure:

1. Shim header: A 4-byte header that indicates the presence of telemetry data. It contains information about the type of INT header following it and the total length of INT header and metadata stack encapsulated between it and UDP payload. The structure of this header is demonstrated in Figure 28.
2. INT header: An 8-byte header that follows the shim header and contains information about the stack of metadata that follows it, such as the length of metadata to be inserted at each node and the remaining number of nodes allowed to add their metadata to the packet. The fields of this header are also clarified in Figure 28.

3. Metadata stack: Following the INT header, it consists of a stack of metadata headers. Each header is inserted by an INT node along the monitored path and contains standard metadata, such as ingress timestamp, egress timestamp, and hop latency.

Our contribution lies in extending the standard in-band telemetry structure not only to monitor standard metadata but also to customize the monitoring operation by tracking new key parameters, which is crucial for optimizing end-to-end network performance, including the UE. These new parameters are the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) of radio link, the geolocation information (GPS longitude, latitude and altitude) and the CPU load. The designed INT can be activated for specific data flows and its structure is shown in Figure 27.

Every node has the flexibility to serve as a source node, transit node or destination node. Furthermore, a single node can perform multiple roles at the same time: it can act as both a source and transit node or as both a destination and transit node for different flows.

FIGURE 28: INT HEADERS

INT source node is the first node in the packet’s path of the INT domain. This node inserts a 12-byte structure (i.e., standard shim and INT header) after the UDP header. Subsequently, the source node acts as a transit node, appending 40 bytes of its metadata information into a metadata header known as ‘Switch Metadata Header’. The information in this header includes both the standard metadata and the

new information specifically tailored for UAV network, as illustrated in Figure 28. The standard information encompasses: 1. Switch ID. 2. Ingress timestamp. 3. Egress timestamp. 4. Hop latency (the difference between egress and ingress timestamp). 5. Flow ID. The new information includes: 1. CPU load. 2. Longitude. 3. Latitude. 4. Altitude. 5. The RSSI of the incoming radio interface.

At the next INT transit node, 40 bytes of information are appended to a metadata header called 'Second Switch Metadata Header'. All these metadata headers have the same structure as the Switch Metadata Header illustrated in. This process is repeated for each subsequent INT transit node along the monitored path. Eventually, at the sink node, the received packet is duplicated using the P4 clone function. The payload is removed from the cloned packet and the sink node sends it, along with its own metadata information, as a final report to the collector.

in parallel, the sink node removes all the INT information from the original packet and forwards it to the receiver. Figure 29 demonstrates the P4 pipeline architecture.

FIGURE 29: P4 PIPELINE ARCHITECTURE

The considered P4 implementation is based on the V1 architectural model specified in the reference P4 software switch, the Behavioral Model version 2 (BMv2).

The model includes several stages:

1. The parser: It is represented by a finite state machine, where the states are responsible for extracting data from the individual header struct into runtime variables. Transitions within the state machine occur conditionally, depending on the value of a parsed header field.
2. Ingress and egress control blocks: each block consists of several match-action tables that match the packet based on different header fields and determine the appropriate actions to take when a match is detected. It also defines a control function that decides the order in which the tables should be executed. The ingress stage is utilized to perform forwarding, while the egress pipeline is utilized to perform further operations after determining the output port for forwarding.
3. The deparser: Its role involves converting the modified headers back into a serialized format within the packet, preparing it for transmission to the subsequent switch in the network. State transitions are determined by the examination of a specific header field, indicating the presence of the subsequent protocol.

The parser subsequently processes UDP, Shim, and INT headers. Ultimately, it extracts the header from the packet, characterized by a variable length with a predefined maximum size. This header represents a stack of metadata headers, including information appended by every transit node. In order to parse the appropriate variable length of this header at each node, the parsing process has been achieved based on the length field in the Shim header. This field encompasses the total length of Shim header, INT header and the stack of metadata headers (Sw mheader) in 4-byte words. By subtracting the length of the Shim header (1 word) and the length of the INT header (2 words) from the value of this field and converting the result from words to bits, the correct length for parsing this header is determined.

After parsing, packets proceed through the ingress pipeline, depicted in Figure 29, where three flow tables are executed: Forwarding, Activate Source and Activate sink. The Forwarding table determines the output port based on Layer 2 (L2) MAC addresses, essentially implementing switch behaviour. The Activate Source table initiates the INT process by invoking the associated action. This action involves inserting both Shim and INT headers into INT packets received at a designated port with a specific UDP port.

Additionally, it updates the length of IP and UDP headers to accommodate the new headers. Meanwhile, the Activate sink table is responsible for duplicating INT packets by executing the relevant action for packets destined for a particular interface with a specific UDP port.

In the egress pipeline, the control function directly triggers the addition of metadata through the 'adding metadata' action. This action retrieves INT metadata from various registers (CPU load, Antenna power register, Geo-latitude, Geo-longitude, and Geo-altitude registers), and writes them into the corresponding header fields. It also decreases the number of hops by 1 and assigns this modified value to the remaining hop field in the INT header, which determines the number of traversed nodes. Finally, it updates the lengths of the IP, UDP, and Shim headers to accommodate the new metadata information added by the node. The table 'Report Forwarding', adopted at the last node of the chain, is tasked with altering the destination of the duplicated INT packet (report) by modifying the MAC address of this packet.

7.3.3 Usage and Interfaces

Activation of the proposed solution relies on P4-runtime, with the configuration of proper flow entries to activate INT generation for a specific flow.

7.3.4 Evaluation

Functional validation

A functional validation has been implemented in a 4 nodes testbed. An API in Linux has been launched on each node to collect information about the antenna power of wireless interfaces, CPU load, and geo-location information. It gathers geo-location information from a Global Positioning System (GPS) device using a Python script that utilizes the gpsd library. This library facilitates interaction with GPS devices through the gpsd service. Then, the API writes this information inside the appropriate register and updates these values every 1 second. Three flows of traffic with different destination UDP ports (i.e., 12345, 12344, 12343) have been generated in P4S4. The three flows are injected into the P4S container for processing. Here the P4S4 acts as a source node, selectively inserting shim and INT headers only

into the flows destined for UDP ports 12345 and 12343, based on predefined flow entries, shown in Figure 30.

The switch adds its metadata to these two flows and forwards the three flows to P4S2. P4S2, in turn, appends its metadata to the incoming flows and forwards the three flows to P4S1, the sink node.

The figure shows that the length of the ingress packets is 44Bytes for the three flows. After the addition of the INT header, related to each node, 12 + 40 bytes are added (resulting length of 96Bytes).

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
1	0.000000000	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12345 Len=2
2	1.047799469	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12344 Len=2
3	2.103186017	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12343 Len=2

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
1	0.000000000	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	96	54321 → 12345 Len=54
2	1.051752900	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12344 Len=2
3	2.111200663	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	96	54321 → 12343 Len=54

FIGURE 30: TRAFFIC CAPTURE IN THE EXPERIMENT, WITH INGRESS TRAFFIC (NO INT) IN THE TOP AND AUGMENTED TRAFFIC IN THE BOTTOM

In the implementation, the maximum path length is assumed equal to 6, with a maximum INT size of 252 bytes in the worst case (at the sink node).

End-to-end latency

The purpose of this set of experiments is to check the ability of the P4S container to process FINT information with a limited additional latency compared to the latency introduced with standard forwarding, with variable topology of P4S nodes with different path depths and variable traffic. Moreover, we investigate the ability of the P4S container to manage and process FINT information for any switch role (source, transit and sink). The impact of data plane programmability in terms of accumulated latency was evaluated. The ICMP traffic has been used for the generation of packets at variable rates. The latency is evaluated as a function of the traffic bitrate and path length, ranging from a minimum of 2 to a

maximum of 4 nodes. In these experiments, the Round Trip Time (RTT) latency measured by Ping includes all the P4-UE system, with a wireless interface and nodes connected with wired links.

Ping packets are generated externally to the P4S container and are routed inside the P4S container which processes the packet.

In the set of measurements without INT, each switch was configured only in static forwarding mode, allowing pings to be routed to the next hop in a bidirectional fashion. In the set of measurements with INT, the P4S has been populated with flow rules to correctly manage the INT. Then, a first INT stack was configured up to the sink node. The sink node eliminates all INT headers and forwards the ping request packet to the external radio interface of the last node. The interface responds with a ping reply in the backward direction. In this case, the local node acts as the source node for a new INT stack backwards to the source. The experienced RTT results are shown in Table 2 when varying the rate of the packet per second (p/s) and the number of the switches.

TABLE 2: RTT MEASUREMENTS

Rate (p/s)	RTT without INT			RTT with INT by		
	2 switches	3 switches	4 switches	2 switches	3 switches	4 switches
1	4.896	6.953	14.243	5.627	8.980	13.276
10	5.164	6.461	13.045	5.712	8.980	12.991
100	4.272	5.687	10.895	5.103	8.980	11.217
1000	4.039	6.595	9.470	5.830	8.980	10.037

The table shows that the additional contribution due to INT processing is always less than 0.5 ms per node in a single direction. The non-linear latency values concerning data plane bitrate are attributed to the behaviour of the BMv2 container which is well known in the literature [31]. Specifically, the switch demonstrates superior performance within an aggregate bitrate range of 150 to 800 Mbit/s, exhibiting increased latency at lower bitrate. However, it is clearly noticed that the latency is always less than 5ms per node, with or without INT.

7.4 RAN Telemetry Exposure

In 5G and beyond, telemetry enables dynamic network adjustments based on real-time data analysis. For example, data collected from Distributed Units (DUs), Radio Units (RUs), and Central Units (CUs) help optimize resource usage, balance loads, and improve energy efficiency across the network. The integration of AI and Machine Learning (ML) further enhances telemetry's role, as AI algorithms use telemetry data to automate network management, enabling near-instant adjustments to optimize performance and energy use.

Looking ahead to 6G, the role of RAN telemetry will expand significantly. Emerging technologies such as Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS), Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), and advanced spectrum management strategies will all depend on robust telemetry systems to function efficiently. Dynamic spectrum re-farming, for example, will rely heavily on real-time telemetry data to make decisions regarding spectrum allocation and interference management. Without accurate and timely telemetry data, these innovations would be challenging to implement effectively.

Additionally, Open RAN (O-RAN) architectures play a critical role in advancing telemetry systems. O-RAN introduces the RAN Intelligent Controllers (RIC), both in Near-RT and Non-RT forms, which use telemetry data to drive intelligent network decisions. These RICs ingest data from various sources in the RAN, process it using AI/ML models, and make real-time decisions that optimize network performance. Telemetry serves as the backbone of this decision-making process, ensuring that the network remains responsive and adaptive to changing conditions, including fluctuations in traffic, mobility patterns, and resource availability.

Furthermore, 6G networks are expected to integrate more diverse data sources, such as environmental sensors and positioning systems, which will feed additional telemetry data into the system. This expanded scope of telemetry will enable networks to not only optimize performance but also address broader goals such as reducing electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure and improving user experience in urban and rural environments.

7.4.1 Novelty Beyond the State-of-the-Art

The Open RAN (O-RAN) architecture represents a significant evolution in how telemetry is collected, processed, and used for network optimization. Traditional RAN systems typically rely on vendor-specific solutions that are tightly coupled with proprietary hardware, limiting flexibility and innovation. O-RAN breaks away from this paradigm by introducing open, standardized interfaces (such as E2, O1, and A1), which facilitate the integration of third-party applications (xApps and rApps) for telemetry collection and control.

In O-RAN systems, the RAN Intelligent Controllers (RIC) – both in their near-real-time (Near-RT) and non-real-time (Non-RT) forms – play a crucial role in leveraging telemetry data to optimize network performance. The Near-RT RIC enables real-time adjustments by collecting telemetry data from network elements such as DUs and RUs. This data is used to drive optimizations in areas like resource scheduling, energy efficiency, and user mobility. The Non-RT RIC, on the other hand, is responsible for longer-term network planning and policy management, often using machine learning (ML) models trained on historical telemetry data to make informed decisions.

A key innovation in this project lies in extending telemetry collection to include non-O-RAN-compliant elements. Many networks still contain legacy systems or proprietary devices that do not fully adhere to O-RAN standards. Traditional telemetry frameworks are often limited in their ability to integrate data from these non-compliant components. This project introduces a flexible telemetry architecture that bridges the gap between O-RAN and non-O-RAN systems, allowing data from proprietary sensors, legacy infrastructure, or even custom-built radios to be collected and processed alongside standardized O-RAN components O-RAN Alliance.

Another novel feature is the system's ability to handle more diverse data sources. As 6G technologies evolve, the network will need to process telemetry from new types of devices and systems, such as environmental sensors, user equipment with advanced sensing capabilities, and infrastructure providing Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS). These devices introduce new data streams that traditional RAN telemetry systems were not designed to handle. The extended telemetry framework is capable of ingesting and processing this wider variety of data, enabling more sophisticated network optimizations,

such as dynamic spectrum re-farming, real-time interference management, and energy-efficient network configurations.

Furthermore, advancements in programmable telemetry, such as the RANsight platform, are revolutionizing the way telemetry data is collected and exposed within the RAN. Programmable telemetry allows for highly customizable data collection pipelines, where network operators can specify the exact metrics they want to collect and how they want to process them. This flexibility enables more granular control over network operations and allows for real-time adjustments to be made based on precise, localized data. These advancements in programmable telemetry have far-reaching implications, especially for AI-driven network management, which relies on vast amounts of accurate and timely data to function effectively.

Lastly, recent updates to the O-RAN specifications have introduced enhanced support for telemetry collection and management. The latest revisions to the O1 and E2 interfaces have refined how telemetry data is transmitted between network components and the RICs, improving both the speed and accuracy of data transmission. These updates also include expanded support for new use cases, such as network slicing and autonomous vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communications. By building on these developments, this project ensures that the telemetry system is future-proof, capable of supporting the rapidly evolving demands of next-generation networks O-RAN Alliance.

DESIRE6G architecture supports programmable data plane implementation where in network functions like CU-UP are realised as P4 programmable data plane components which run in CPUs, Smart NIC cards or Tofino switches. This introduces the scope for P4 INT (in band network telemetry) which can expose telemetry to all routers and switches in the packet data network. This allows for run-time optimisation of network paths taken by the packets including QoS. RAN telemetry collected via E2 interface is exposed to near RT RIC. The near RT RIC publishes this telemetry data to Kafka data bus as JSON messages. The desire 6G INT framework reads data from Kafka bus and exposes this data to MAS agents in near-RT RIC as well as non-RT RIC. The MAS agents perform runtime optimisation of user plane by interacting with SDN controller in non RT RIC based on this telemetry data.

7.4.2 Implementation

The Telemetry Collector Architecture is inside the Accelleran's dRAX is designed to gather, process, and distribute telemetry data across a diverse range of network components, both compliant and non-compliant with O-RAN standards. The architecture comprises three main blocks: Input Interfaces, Translators, and Output Interfaces. These blocks work together to ensure seamless data collection, transformation, and dissemination, supporting real-time network optimization and decision-making processes.

TELEMETRY COLLECTOR GENERAL ARCH

FIGURE 31: TELEMETRY COLLECTOR ARCHITECTURE

Input Interfaces

The input interfaces are responsible for collecting telemetry data from various sources within the network, including O-RAN-compliant and NON- O-RAN compliant or legacy components. The following key input interfaces are integrated into the system:

- **E2 Interface:** This interface is a core component for collecting telemetry data from O-RAN elements like the DU (Distributed Unit), CU (Centralized Unit), and RU (Radio Unit). The E2 interface facilitates real-time data transmission between these RAN elements and the Near-RT RIC, enabling critical operations such as resource management, mobility control, and interference handling.

- **NATS Protobuf:** This interface is defined inside the dRAX entity and is in charge of bringing information from the Accelleran CU in a Fastly manner to provide fast telemetry interaction.
- **Proprietary UDP:** This input interface supports high-speed data collection from custom-built or non-standardized components. It is tailored for specific use cases where existing protocols may not suffice, ensuring that proprietary network elements can still contribute telemetry data to the system. It is part of the dRAX family interfaces that connect the RIC with the DU.
- **InfluxDB Line Protocol:** Used primarily for time-series data collection, this interface enables the integration of performance metrics and sensor data into the telemetry system. It is particularly useful for monitoring network health over time, feeding data into AI-driven decision-making processes. This is used to connect testers that do not support a fully O-RAN compliant testers or KPI values that not defined in 3GPP metrics.
- **TCP-based Input Interfaces:** These interfaces provide compatibility with legacy or non-O-RAN-compliant systems. The use of general-purpose TCP protocols allows the system to ingest telemetry data from older network elements that do not follow O-RAN standards, ensuring backward compatibility.
- **NATS Messaging:** NATS is used as a messaging protocol to facilitate real-time data transport between distributed components of the network. It is lightweight and scalable, providing low-latency delivery of telemetry data across different parts of the architecture.

These input interfaces allow for a wide variety of telemetry sources to feed data into the system, ensuring that both traditional and modern network elements can be monitored and optimized in real-time.

Translators and Data Processing

Once the telemetry data is collected from the input interfaces, it enters the translators and data processing block. The primary role of this component is to standardize and transform the data into formats that can be processed and acted upon by the network's AI-driven systems.

- **Translators:** These components convert proprietary or non-standard data formats into formats compatible with 3GPP data structures and O-RAN-compliant systems. For instance, data collected from legacy equipment or custom-built devices might use different protocols, but the

translators ensure that this data can still be utilized effectively within the broader network architecture.

- **Transformers:** The transformers are responsible for pre-processing the telemetry data, performing functions like filtering, aggregation, and normalization. These processes ensure that only the most relevant data is passed on to the decision-making components, reducing the processing load while maintaining high accuracy.
- **Converters:** Are the ones in charge of extending the 3GPP data sources into the needed output interfaces for the different parts of the dRAX components and external entities.

This block ensures that data from all sources is presented in a uniform, actionable format, which is then delivered to the output interfaces for distribution to the appropriate decision-making entities.

Output Interfaces

The output interfaces are responsible for disseminating the processed telemetry data to various consumers within the network and to external systems. The primary output interfaces include:

- **O1 VES (Kafka):** This interface streams telemetry data in real time to event-driven systems using the VES (VNF Event Streaming) protocol over Kafka. It allows for integration with third-party systems that require real-time telemetry for analytics, monitoring, or optimization purposes.
- **HTTP for External VES Collectors:** External collectors and monitoring systems can access the telemetry data via HTTP-based interfaces. This makes the data easily consumable by external applications that might not be part of the O-RAN ecosystem but require access to network performance metrics or health data.
- **Future Expansion for 6G Systems:** The architecture is designed with future-proofing in mind, supporting future enhancements such as WebSockets for 3GPP-compliant streaming and high-volume data flows. This ensures that the system can scale and adapt to the needs of emerging 6G technologies, which will require even more sophisticated telemetry systems.

These output interfaces ensure that telemetry data is readily available to key consumers, such as the RICs (Near-RT and Non-RT), AI/ML systems, and external monitoring platforms, facilitating real-time network optimization and troubleshooting.

7.4.3 Scalability and Future Enhancements

The Telemetry Collector Architecture is built with scalability in mind, designed to accommodate the increasing complexity and data volume of 6G networks. As technologies like Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) and Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) become more integrated into the network, the system will need to handle an even greater diversity of data sources.

To support these advancements, the architecture is modular, allowing for the easy addition of new protocols and interfaces as they become necessary. The system's ability to scale horizontally by adding new processing nodes and vertically by increasing its processing power ensures that it can grow with the demands of next-generation networks O-RAN Alliance.

Future iterations of the system will focus on improving the integration of AI and ML into the decision-making process, enabling the network to optimize itself autonomously based on the telemetry data it collects. This will further reduce operational overhead and improve network efficiency, particularly in dense, urban deployments where real-time data processing is critical.

7.5 Software monitoring

7.5.1 Mapping with DESIRE-6G architecture

The possible use of this deep software monitoring in the context of DESIRE6G project is to publish the performance metrics, originated from a network function or a P4 node, as a complementary In-band Network Telemetry (INT) metadata. Hence, path optimization consuming INT is done according to the level of performance of traversed nodes.

7.5.2 Principle

Software runtime monitoring from control flow graph time series extraction is shown below. It consists of probing individual code blocks to deliver individual code block time-to-execute and call frequency metrics. Time series aggregate data used asynchronously to assess if the software executes at a normal pace (i.e., without major distortion to a measure average).

The principle is that when looking at the code in its entirety, its control flow graph is undecidable, hence its execution depends on its several variables. Two executions may lead to a very different quantity of executed instructions. Reversely, when working at code block level with code blocks statically defined, their executions are supposedly processing the same quantity of instructions. Working at code block level allows for more consistent timing measurements based on fixed execution elements.

The method explicitly requires operating code changes on the executed code (i.e., assembly instructions) to insert the probes on code blocks. The deployment process consists of three steps. First, the original executable undergoes both static and dynamic analysis, providing us with reference data. Next, during the patching process, an algorithm identifies the most relevant and performance-friendly locations to insert probes. This results in a patched executable that has been statically rewritten to include monitoring functions. When the patched executable is run, any abnormal behaviour—such as high CPU usage or DDoS attacks—that disrupts the normal functioning of the process will be promptly detected, triggering an alert (Figure 32).

FIGURE 32: OVERVIEW OF THE MONITORING PROCESS

7.5.3 Novelty beyond the state of the art

Several frameworks and tools for software monitoring exist like perf, valgrind, gprof, strace, procpa and deliver timing elements on unchanged code, hence delivering timing measures on the complete execution of the code through installed dependencies (i.e., the monitoring tools). Moreover, typically in the field of telecom network software, network functions are continuously executed without showing a start and an end. This type of software which is crucial for network service performance cannot be performance monitored without working at code block level. In the state of the art, Control Flow Graph Integrity [32][33] monitoring by code changes is used to detect abnormal behaviours possibly caused

by its control flow violation, but without assessing the actual performance ratio. These techniques are known to induce a significant overhead and false alarms, because the placement of (costly) probes is systematic on each code blocks and because the CFG is undecidable by nature. Our solution is designed to insert probes into specific code blocks with high precision, enabling highly accurate performance monitoring without negatively impacting overall process performance.

7.5.4 First experiments, future work and Implementation

Our work does not depart from the performance penalty as stated above. This requires a drastic reduction of the set of instrumented code blocks. Another encountered difficulty lies on the undecidability of the control flow where a jump can take place at any location inside a code block and be directed to an instruction in the middle of another block (i.e., not necessarily its entry). This problem has been reflected with our first experiments which showed a discrepancy in our measures, where code blocks slowdowns were between one and two orders of magnitude higher than for other blocks. Our results indicate that abnormal behaviours, such as external stress applied to the machine, can be detected through variations in block duration and execution frequency. However, the variability in results across different blocks remains significant, making the selection of appropriate blocks for monitoring a critical factor in ensuring accurate detection. We also concluded that some code blocks were somehow short cut and not processed linearly. To reach tangible and usable results, another filtering of monitoring code blocks must be done. This filtering can be done through a pre-deployment stage where the code is stressed and executed without performance constraint (as the code does not execute in real conditions). The selection directly derives from a brute forged time series (of all blocks) which shows the code blocks which have been shortcut for their eviction. Another approach removing ambiguity is to insert a reference code block designed by us and that called at the ideal call frequency for performance penalty. As this code block is unknown, it cannot be a callee in the middle of it or be a caller in the middle of it. The reference code block will be executed from the first instruction to the last instruction for certain. Ideally, the reference code block will be as representative as possible to a real average code block.

One of the first challenges is choosing the appropriate patching method, and we have tested two different approaches (Figure 33). The first method involves using a single trampoline (aka hook) per bloc,

requiring only $n+1$ trampolines to measure n blocks execution time. This method is simpler and less invasive, making it easier to implement. However, it relies on consecutive blocks to provide meaningful information, limiting its effectiveness in scenarios where individual block measurements are needed. The second method uses two trampolines per block, which allows for precise execution time measurement and is suited for selective and one-block patching. While this method offers greater flexibility and accuracy, it comes with significant downsides. It increases the execution time of selected blocks by adding many instructions and requires $2n$ trampolines to measure n blocks, leading to higher complexity and resource consumption.

FIGURE 33: THE TWO PATCHING METHODS

Another task has involved exploring and optimizing the block data extraction process, as this is a significant source of performance overhead. Given its importance, our current approach uses a separate process to read the data from a shared memory segment and store it in a file.

FIGURE 34: BLOCKS DATA EXTRACTION BREAKDOWN

Our work has also gone to the elaboration of three KPIs of confidence, penalty and convergence as stated below:

Confidence: Ability to generate trustworthy and accurate measurements of the global software performance ratio (% speed ratio versus a reference value)

Penalty: The direct CPU costs induced by the monitoring snippets themselves (i.e., creating and buffering time series made of timestamps and block identifiers).

Convergence: The time needed to elaborate good and usable reference measurement as well as elaborate a performance ratio based on the time series.

For the initial static binary patch, we are currently using e9patch⁴, a powerful tool that allows for the insertion of patched code snippets at key control flow graph locations, such as calls and jumps. This capability is particularly useful for tasks like performance monitoring at code blocks level, where tracking the execution of specific instructions is crucial.

7.5.5 Limitations

The method detailed above bears use restrictions, essentially related to the format of the considered payload. Restricted support to x86 compiled binaries: The SECaaS currently process x86 binary files, hence machine compiled. Without stating that a similar type of payload rewriting workflow cannot be worked out for interpreted bytecodes, further technical investigation must be done. This typically applies in the context of DESIRE6G, P4 written payloads, (if they are not compiled for a x86 platform) will not be supported in the course of the project.

7.5.6 Current work status and future works

Our current work is split into the two possible outcomes of better selection of the code blocks or insertion of a reference code block. From this stage onwards, we will benchmark the solution on a set

⁴ <https://github.com/GJDuck/e9patch>

of representative code (DPDK l2fwd, high CPU usage executable) with the aim of converging towards a Penalty of less than 1% while reaching a satisfying confidence and convergence criteria. Our tests are helping us define these criteria, but we plan to further refine the definition of these during our progress. We are also considering the development of an on-demand monitoring architecture that would allow for monitoring to be dynamically activated and deactivated as needed. By implementing this adaptive monitoring mechanism, we aim to strike a balance between capturing detailed performance data and maintaining optimal system efficiency, minimizing the impact on resources when monitoring is not in use.

8 Application and network function acceleration and offloading

To meet the stringent performance requirements of next-generation networks, DESIRE6G leverages hardware accelerators to enhance the throughput and latency performance of both network and application functions. These accelerators enable the offloading of computationally intensive tasks from general-purpose processors to specialized hardware (e.g., FPGAs, GPUs, ASICs, DPUs, smartNICs). This approach improves efficiency, supports scalability, and ensures consistent performance across diverse workloads. The components developed in this area focus on accelerating critical functions, including packet processing, encryption, compression, and AI/ML-based analytics. Additionally, they facilitate seamless integration into the DESIRE6G architecture, aligning with cloud-native principles to ensure flexibility and interoperability.

8.1 Accelerated CU-UP on SmartNIC

The Open RAN (O-RAN⁵) architecture represents a paradigm shift from the traditional, monolithic Radio Access Network (RAN) model to a disaggregated and virtualized deployment approach. By introducing standardized function splits and open interface definitions, O-RAN allows operators to deploy and operate networks with great flexibility and adaptability in a cloud-native environment, supporting many use cases with varying requirements. While virtualization offers operational flexibility and potential for continuous evolution using commodity hardware like general-purpose processors (GPPs), it also introduces communication and processing overheads in a disaggregated RAN deployment [34], specifically for the lower layers of the cellular protocol stack, that involve quite heavy processing [35][36][39]. GPPs face challenges in satisfying the stringent latency requirements and high data rates posed by diverse use cases in the next generation mobile networks, while horizontal scaling is not future proof, as high network bandwidth demand cannot be supported without significant cost [37]. To

⁵ <https://www.o-ran.org/>

overcome these limitations, hardware accelerators like FPGAs, DPUs etc., are introduced. The open RAN architecture further opens the possibility to tailor user-plane functions using hardware accelerators, which is important to meet the stringent latency and data rates requirements posed by diverse use cases in the next generation mobile networks.

Focusing on the Centralized Unit (CU), it consists of two parts, the control plane (CU-CP) and the user plane (CU-UP). The CU-CP is tasked with Radio Resource Control (RRC - managing UE connections to the RAN - whereas the CU-UP is implementing the Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP), and the Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP). The SDAP mainly deals with QoS flow mapping, while the PDCP, defined in TS 38.323 by 3GPP, supports functionalities like transmission buffering, packet re-ordering, packet de-/duplication, header compression, ciphering, and integrity checks. The CU-UP also handles GPRS Tunnelling Protocol (GTP) tunnel encapsulation in the upstream and downstream. Accelerating the CU-UP protocol layers is essential for meeting the performance demands of high-throughput and low-latency applications in next-generation networks. By offloading network functions to the network elements, such as onto SmartNICs, we can minimize the packet processing overhead of the GPPs in servers. Additionally, using dedicated hardware accelerators for computationally intensive tasks, such as cryptographic processing within the PDCP layer, further improves processing speed and efficiency of network packets. These enhancements not only improve the data processing efficiency of CU-UP but also strengthen the resource utilization and energy efficiency in RAN, enabling it to support a higher density of connected devices and meet stringent QoS requirements.

Extreme Data Path (XDP) [34] is an eBPF program type that is designed to be hooked in the earliest point of packet reception in the Linux kernel. It provides a way to efficiently process packets before they reach the network stack, allowing for reduced latency and improved throughput. XDP programs also support to be offloaded to SmartNICs, allowing for additional performance gains by handling packet processing directly on specialized network hardware. DESIER6G aims to leverage and evaluate XDP

together with SmartNICs like NVIDIA BlueField⁶ and Netronome Agilio CX⁷, to accelerate packet processing within the Centralized Unit - User Plane (CU-UP) of the O-RAN architecture.

8.1.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Hardware acceleration and offloading are essential to meet the performance requirements of next-generation cellular networks. These techniques help alleviate the load on traditional CPU and Linux kernel-based packet processing [34][40]. XDP is one of the offloading techniques that has been widely explored in mobile networks, such as User Plane Function (UPF) acceleration in core networks, security and network telemetry [41][42][43]. A preliminary design for an XDP-based CU-UP has also been proposed without implementation and evaluation [44]; however, this design relies entirely on XDP kernel programs that operate on a per-packet basis, which limits its ability to support packet reordering and buffering required by the PDCP layer. To overcome these limitations, we propose implementing an AF_XDP-based user space application to manage slow-path packets that requires packet reordering or buffering. AF_XDP, a socket type within the XDP framework, allows for high-performance packet processing in user space by bypassing the traditional networking layers in the kernel. This enables direct access to the network interface card (NIC), reducing latency and increasing data throughput [45]. Furthermore, this will be the first functional implementation and evaluation of CU-UP protocol layers utilizing XDP.

8.1.2 Design and implementation

Figure 35 illustrates the XDP data-path for the CU-UP driven by the limitations associated with XDP offloading on Netronome Agilio SmartNICs. Netronome SmartNICs can only support XDP programs to a maximum instruction size of approximately 8,000 instructions and a map entry size limit of 64 bytes, which constrains the implementation of complex protocol operations, as they can easily exceed this limit. Since XDP programs operate on a per-packet basis, they are inherently limited in their capacity to

⁶ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/networking/products/data-processing-unit/>

⁷ <https://netronome.com/agilio-smartnics/>

perform packet reordering and buffering, which are essential functions of the PDCP layer. Furthermore, the cryptographic accelerator on Netronome SmartNICs is inaccessible from within XDP programs, thus restricting the support for encryption and decryption tasks within the data-path.

FIGURE 35: OVERVIEW OF THE DESIGN OF XDP-BASED CU-UP (UPLINK PATH)

To address these limitations, our design employs a partial offloading model. The fast path within the kernel is responsible for packet forwarding when reordering is disabled due to fast processing requirements e.g., for real-time applications. However, if reordering or buffering is required, packets are redirected from the kernel to a user-space application via the AF_XDP socket (xsk) (See Figure 35). This approach bypasses the standard Linux network stack and leverages UMEM to share packet data between the kernel and user space, enabling zero-copy forwarding to improve efficiency. To access the cryptographic accelerator on Netronome SmartNICs and handle computationally intensive cryptographic operations, we propose using custom P4 processing to offload these tasks onto the SmartNIC.

8.1.3 Usage and Interfaces

Currently we are in the process of developing the XDP solution, using the open-source srsRAN project with support of split7.2/split8 from Software Radio System [46]. The CU-UP interfaces conform to the ORAN specifications. The build and deployment process procedures are the same as srsRAN.

Additionally, we are automating processes to simplify and expedite the deployment of our customized XDP solution on Kubernetes, making deployment and management more efficient.

8.1.4 Limitations and future plans

We plan to continue implementing majority of CU-UP functionalities including SDAP, PDCP and GTP-U protocols. Due to the limitations of XDP offloading on Netronome SmartNICs, our design will require a significant portion of the computation to be handled within the host system, either in the kernel or in a user-level application. Therefore, we plan to investigate the offloading possibilities in Nvidia BlueField SmartNics. Although NVIDIA BlueField does not support XDP offloading, it can run ARM Linux distributions that natively support XDP programs [47], potentially enabling the CU-UP stack to operate fully within the network interface.

8.2 Offloading of security network functions to Bluefield NICs

Traditionally, security functions such as firewalls, intrusion detection, and DDoS mitigation are performed by general-purpose CPUs. However, these functions are resource-intensive, and as network traffic grows, CPUs become bottlenecks. SmartNICs, such as the NVIDIA Bluefield Data Processing Unit (DPU), offer a powerful alternative by offloading these network functions, improving throughput, reducing latency, and enhancing scalability. Specifically, offloading security functions to the Bluefield-2 DPU allows for hardware-accelerated processing and real-time protection at the network edge.

For instance, in a DDoS attack scenario, real-time telemetry data is critical for detecting and mitigating abnormal traffic patterns. With Bluefield NICs, telemetry analysis and anomaly detection can be conducted at line-speed, reducing response times and limiting the impact of an attack.

In 5G networks, the User Plane Function (UPF) plays a key role in handling user traffic. Implementing the UPF on a P4-based programmable switch and programming INT Reports generation of GTP streams, real time features can be submitted to an accelerated function that extracts features in real time for AI-

based inference, or directly implements in-network AI (e.g., leveraging on internal CPU, or even GPU resources of the Bluefield-2) to detect and mitigate security attacks.

8.2.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The following aspects represents the novelties of the introduction of security functions embedded in data plane including P4 collectors and Smart-NIC accelerations:

- Integration of P4 Programmability: Leverages P4-based User-Plane Functions (UPFs) to enhance data-plane programmability, enabling advanced telemetry collection and packet processing.
- Deep Learning Model: Implements a CNN-based anomaly detection mechanism tailored for DDoS detection, achieving high accuracy (98.6%) and F1-score (98%).
- Two-Stage Telemetry Collection: Combines efficient data compression and preprocessing using Fastcapa with scalable packet processing, supporting 100 Gbps traffic.
- Real-Time Analysis: Utilizes telemetry data in real-time to detect and mitigate DDoS attacks, outperforming traditional methods by addressing traffic at both packet and flow levels

8.2.2 Design and implementation

In the preliminary implementation of this security use case in 5G UPF, called 5G DDoS Attack Detection (5G-DAD), the utilized architecture is shown in Figure 36.

FIGURE 36: SECURITY FUNCTION OFFLOADING: 5GDAD ARCHITECTURE

Data Net comprises regular and malicious node generating DDoS attacks towards the GNodeB hosts. Programmable UPF are designed to export INT Reports of GTP to the DPDK-enabled Fastcapa

Telemetry Collector. Features are extracted here and sent to a CNN system that performs DDoS detection. The same system is used to build the dataset to train the CNN, relying on dedicated Kafka topics and an Influx DB database to store the classified samples and related features. The initial implementation will include the Bluefield-2 onboarding the Fastcapa functionality. Future releases will include the possibility to onboard the AI stage, possibly relying on the DPU with embedded GPU.

8.2.3 Usage and interfaces

The proposed framework uses a P4-based User-Plane Function (UPF) to leverage the programmability of the data plane for advanced telemetry and traffic management. The P4-programmed switches act as the central component for capturing and processing telemetry data, ensuring flexible and efficient network monitoring. These switches are integrated with SmartNIC Data Processing Units (DPUs), which offloads computationally intensive tasks from the CPU. This offloading improves performance and enables real-time processing of high-bandwidth traffic. Telemetry collection is managed in two stages. First, a P4 telemetry collector gathers and compresses data directly from the network. Then, a second stage preprocesses the telemetry packets using the DPDK-based Fastcapa framework, which enables scalable and rapid packet processing at wire speed. The preprocessed telemetry is stored in an InfluxDB database, where it is used for training and inference with the CNN-based detection model. The CNN analyzes patterns in the telemetry data, such as packet flow rates, inter-arrival times, and header information, to detect DDoS attacks with high accuracy. The framework also integrates visualization tools for operators to monitor network performance and anomalies in real time.

Testing and evaluation of the system were carried out using Docker containers, simulating various real-world attack scenarios. The experimental setup includes malicious nodes generating DDoS attacks and normal traffic nodes, with the P4 switches processing UPF-based GTP traffic management (interfaces N3-N6-N9) and telemetry generation towards the smartNIC.

8.2.4 Results, limitations and future plans

Preliminary results show that, for 100 Gbps traffic with 1512B length, more than 8 million telemetry packets are generated per second by each P4 switch. The telemetry processing system takes 120 ns to process each packet. With a DPDK-based telemetry worker system, we use up to 5 CPU cores to process telemetry packets within a single pipeline designed to handle 100 Gbps. The Fastcapa server provides five types of DPDK workers on each CPU core to handle tasks such as pulling packets, ACL control, flow handling, Kafka topics handling, TCP connection maintenance, and CSV file generation. Results also show that the CNN is able to detect DDoS packets with 98.6% accuracy.

One limitation of the framework lies in its current focus on detecting and mitigating DDoS attacks. While effective for this type of threat, it does not yet address other significant security concerns, such as advanced persistent threats (APTs) or zero-day exploits, which are also critical in the 5G and 6G contexts. Another limitation is its reliance on specialized hardware, such as DPUs, which, while enhancing performance, may limit deployment in environments without such resources. Additionally, the dataset used for training and evaluation was collected in a controlled testbed environment. While this guarantees consistent results, it may not fully capture the variability and complexity of real-world traffic patterns, potentially impacting the generalization of the model.

Future work aims to address these limitations by extending the tool towards a hybrid AI-native UPF for 6G networks. This would integrate advanced capabilities, such as optimized hardware offloading for AI tasks and enhanced support for diverse traffic patterns. The detection framework will also be expanded to cover a broader range of security threats, improving its adaptability and robustness in various scenarios. Furthermore, ongoing research will focus on optimizing the telemetry collection and preprocessing stages to reduce latency and enhance scalability.

All the details of the implementation and results are reported in [48], presented at the HPSR conference in July 2024.

8.3 Accelerated Neural Network Execution

The SOL Neural Network compiler was described in D4.1 [1]. During the last reporting period, significant advancements were made in the development of the SOL Neural Network Compiler, leading to the release of versions 0.5.3 and 0.6.0. These updates introduced key benefits such as enhanced performance through experimental features like vLLM support and CUDA Graphs integration in PyTorch, improved ease of use with Keras integration, and the reinstatement of CUDA support for GPU acceleration.

Furthermore, we developed the SOL server with the objective of providing optimization of neural network models for the users of the Desire6G platform.

8.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Optimizing neural networks for both training and inference is an emerging area of machine learning development, with various solutions available to achieve faster and more efficient results. Among these, the majority focuses on hyperparameter optimization and search space exploration. Nvidia TensorRT⁸ [49] and Intel OpenVino⁹ [50] go further, offering comprehensive solutions for model compression, optimization, and inference acceleration.

Both TensorRT and OpenVino support inference only and cannot optimize the training phase. While TensorRT focuses on NVIDIA GPUs, OpenVino instead support only x86 CPUs and Intel hardware platforms. In this context, SOL emerges for its versatility, as it supports both inference and training, and multiple hardware platforms, such as x86 and ARM processors, NVIDIA GPUs and the NEC Sx-Aurora Tsubasa Vector Engine.

⁸ <https://developer.nvidia.com/tensorrt-getting-started>

⁹ <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/developer/tools/opencv-toolkit/overview.html>

8.3.2 Implementation

8.3.2.1 SOL compiler

Experimental support for vLLM. In its experimental phase, vLLM¹⁰ integration into SOL focuses on optimizing large language model (LLM) inference and serving. This experimental support aims to reduce memory overhead and improve throughput for large models, making it possible to handle extensive models more efficiently. The integration allows for running sol-optimized large language models to run and be served through the vLLM library.

Experimental support for CUDAGraphs. SOL now supports CUDA Graphs in PyTorch, that significantly optimizes GPU performance by reducing kernel launch overhead, allowing multiple GPU kernels to be grouped together and executed as a single graph. This process avoids the repetitive overhead of launching individual GPU kernels for every operation during model training or inference. This feature aligns with SOL's goal of improving execution efficiency across various deep learning workloads, making it especially useful for large models and high-performance environments.

CUDA support. We restored CUDA support, with better compatibility for CUDA-enabled GPUs. CUDA provides developers with direct access to the virtual instruction set and memory of the parallel computational elements in GPUs, enabling highly efficient execution of complex computational tasks, such as deep learning model training and inference.

The update added support for BFloat16 and Float16 precision, contributing to more efficient neural network execution on NVIDIA hardware. Further, CUDA integration improvements allow more seamless handling of complex neural networks and faster execution times.

Experimental Keras integration. SOL has expanded its support to include Keras integration, allowing TensorFlow users to benefit from SOL's optimizations without extensive code changes. This feature enables smooth compatibility and performance enhancements in Keras models.

¹⁰ <https://docs.vllm.ai/en/latest/>

8.3.2.2 SOL server

We defined a RESTful API that allows the SMO to send a model to the SOL server to request its optimization and finally adding the optimized model to its catalogue. Figure 37 shows an example where a generic user initiates an optimization request by reaching out to the SMO, which in turn forward it to the SOL server. The server replies to the SMO with a UUID, which univocally identifies that model, and starts the optimization. As the model optimization can take up to a few minutes, we developed the service in an asynchronous fashion, to avoid the timeout of the request from the SMO.

Then, the SMO periodically requests to the server the optimized model by using the UUID. When the model is ready, the server replies with a binary package. The package contains: i) an executable that can be run from command line; ii) some libraries needed to run the executable.

FIGURE 37: SOL SERVER INTERACTIONS

8.3.3 Usage and Interfaces

The SOL server is a RESTful API developed with FastAPI¹¹. Figure 38 shows the swagger UI of the two server endpoints. The first one is a POST operation for the model upload, associated to a generic user. It

¹¹ <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com>

requires as parameters: a file, a username, the model's name, and a list of parameters of the model. The response is a string containing the UUID for that model and user. The second endpoint is a GET operation for retrieving the optimized model, which requires the UUID. The response in this case can be: i) the binary package of the optimized model; ii) a message notifying that the package is not ready yet; iii) an error message if the model could not be compiled.

FIGURE 38: SOL SERVER ENDPOINTS

8.3.4 Evaluation

To evaluate the SOL compiler, we optimized different neural networks, originally implemented in PyTorch. We tested three popular computer vision networks: Alexnet, Densenet and Mobilenet. During the experiments, we measured the latency per inference, the number of inferences per second and the time gain during training compared to PyTorch. We performed the measurements in a NVIDIA GPU and in an x86 CPU.

The results are shown in Table 3. The best results are highlighted in bold. SOL exhibits almost in all cases a better performance than PyTorch. The latency per inference (measured with batch size 1) is well below 1 milliseconds in GPU and a few milliseconds in CPU, while the inferences per second (measure with batch size 128) are below 1 thousand in CPU and a few tens of thousands in GPU. During training, SOL guarantees a gain up to 3 times against PyTorch.

TABLE 3: SOL BENCHMARKING

KPI	Hardware	Framework	Alexnet	Shufflenet	Mobilenet
Latency per inference [msec]	GPU	SOL	0.51	0.59	0.24
		PyTorch	0.90	5.05	4.10
	CPU	SOL	2.80	7.91	8.36
		PyTorch	15.15	18.19	18.53
Inferences per second [1e3]	GPU	SOL	28.45	25.80	10.59
		PyTorch	25.36	18.91	5.03
	CPU	SOL	0.888	0.614	0.124
		PyTorch	0.797	0.989	0.073
Training time gain (vs PyTorch)	GPU	-	x1.1	x2.28	x1.1
	CPU	-	x3.6	x3.44	x1.85

8.3.5 Limitations and further plans

Concerning the SOL server, we identify as a limitation the need of exporting dependency binaries along with the model executable. We are considering packing the dependencies together with the executable, in a future SOL compiler version. Besides, we will keep evolving the SOL compiler with new features. Finally, we will provide refinements to the SOL server for the handling of the exceptions.

8.4 Remote hardware accelerators in applications with vAccel

The vAccel framework is designed to facilitate seamless access to diverse hardware accelerators in remote or cloud environments. Unlike traditional hardware acceleration frameworks, which often rely on specific libraries or hardware calls, vAccel abstracts functionality to expose high-level, application-specific operations (e.g., image classification, object detection), rather than low-level calls (e.g., CUDA or OpenCL). This approach provides applications with a uniform, easy-to-use interface, regardless of the underlying hardware, making it suitable for deployment across various edge devices (e.g., NVIDIA Jetson, Raspberry Pis, Smart NICs and switches etc.) and cloud servers. At its core, vAccel provides a dispatch handler mechanism that maps application-level API calls to the appropriate underlying plugin, seamlessly integrating with different accelerators without requiring application modification. By focusing on high-level operations, vAccel empowers developers to harness hardware acceleration without direct dependency on any single accelerator library.

8.4.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

vAccel's unique design addresses several limitations of existing hardware acceleration frameworks:

- **Flexible Abstraction and Dispatch:** Unlike frameworks that expose device-specific calls, vAccel abstracts functionality into generalized operations. The core library acts as a dispatch handler, routing API requests to the appropriate plugins, which implement the underlying functionality. This architecture removes the need for device-specific application code, making vAccel adaptable across diverse hardware.
- **Interoperability and Ease of Use:** With the ability to change the plugin to match the target accelerator, the same binary application can leverage different hardware simply by selecting an alternate plugin. This seamless interchangeability offers significant flexibility for deployments in heterogeneous environments, particularly across edge and cloud.
- **Edge-Focused:** While traditional frameworks focus on IoT devices or cloud-only environments, vAccel is optimized specifically for edge nodes (like Jetsons or Raspberry Pi devices) and cloud servers, aligning with the rising demand for edge computing power.

8.4.2 Implementation

The vAccel framework is implemented as a lightweight and modular system, comprised of several key components:

- **vAccel API:** This API exposes high-level operations abstracted from underlying hardware-specific calls, allowing applications to interact with accelerators in terms of operations (e.g., “classify_image”) rather than accelerator-specific functions.
- **Core Library as Dispatch Handler:** The core library’s primary role is to serve as a dispatch handler, mapping high-level API calls to the corresponding plugins that implement the specific hardware functionality. This handler ensures that applications interact with generalized operations (e.g., “classify_image”) rather than hardware-specific calls.
- **Plugins:** Hardware-specific plugins (e.g., implementing operations such as “classify_image” or more fine-grained ones, like MMUL) can be swapped or selected dynamically, enabling transparent access to a range of accelerator implementations without changing application binaries. Plugins are essentially glue codes that map vAccel’s API operations to the hardware-specific implementation of the operation.
- **Transport Layer:** For remote acceleration, vAccel utilizes the plugin system. We implement RPC-based plugins that forward requests to a remote “agent”, which is essentially a simple vAccel application. This process enables secure and efficient communication between low-end edge nodes and nodes with hardware accelerators.

8.4.3 Usage and Interfaces

vAccel offers an intuitive API with flexibility to match operational needs:

- **API Calls Mapped by the Core Library:** The core library maps API calls for task offloading to the relevant plugin, enabling high-level tasks like image inference to be dispatched to local or remote accelerators.

- **Plugin-Based Flexibility:** Users can select plugins suited to specific hardware targets, making it possible for the same application binary to operate across various accelerators by changing the plugin.

The vAccel API is documented at its documentation website¹², whereas lab tutorials¹³ and getting started guides¹⁴ are available for fast onboarding of applications.

8.4.4 Evaluation

The evaluation of the vAccel framework is ongoing. Initial integration with NEC's SOL framework has shown that in local execution the overhead is negligible. In the following table we show some initial performance numbers.

TABLE 4: VACCEL EVALUATION RESULTS

KPI	Framework	Alexnet	Densenet	Mobilenet
Latency per inference [msec]	SOL	0.13	-	-
	PyTorch	0.37	-	-
	vAccel-SOL	0.14		
Inferences per second [1e3]	SOL	7.3	-	-
	PyTorch	2.68	-	-
	vAccel-SOL	7.09	-	-

8.4.5 Limitations and further plans

Currently, vAccel is focused on edge and cloud servers. Future work will focus on expanding vAccel's plugin system to support additional transport options, enhance interoperability in heterogeneous

¹² <https://docs.vaccel.org>

¹³ <https://github.com/nubificus/vaccel-tutorials>

¹⁴ <https://docs.vaccel.org/quickstart/>

environments, and improve performance for latency-sensitive applications. We are in the process of integrating additional frameworks for inferencing, focusing on the efficient transport of models and input/output data.

vAccel is an open-source project¹⁵ developed within NUBIS. The code is freely available under the Apache-2.0 license.

8.5 Tofino implementation of PREOF

In Section 8.3 of deliverable D2.2, PREOF-DetNet is presented as a deterministic solution applied to the transport network to enhance network reliability. Now, we will focus on how this implementation has been carried out using P4 (via Tofino switches) and DPDK. The implementation is based on IETF Standards RFC 8655 [51], RFC 8964 [52], and RFC 9550 [53].

DetNet has its protocol stack, as shown in Figure 39, consisting of two layers: Service and Forwarding. For the Forwarding layer, we use the MPLS-TE protocol. While for the Service layer is further divided into two sublayers: DetNet Control Word and S-Label.

FIGURE 39: DETNET PROTOCOL STACK.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/nubificus/vaccel>

Two fields stand out in these layers:

- seqNumber: This is used to identify packets within a DetNet flow and is in the first sublayer.
- FlowId: This is in the S-Label, and through this field, we identify different DetNet flows.

8.5.1 Implementation

PREOF consists of three functions: Replication, Elimination, and Ordering. The first two have been implemented in P4 using three Tofino switches. However, the ordering functionality has been implemented using DPDK on a server.

We present DetNet-PREOF within a scenario comprising a conventional IP domain, and a deterministic domain. Any packet inside the deterministic domain will include the three headers defined in the DetNet protocol stack.

8.5.1.1 Replication and Elimination Functions – P4 – Tofino switches

All nodes involved in PREOF have the appropriate implementation to support ARP (a protocol essential for conducting tests in the TID laboratory) and MPLS (Forwarding layer of the DetNet protocol stack).

Each time a packet enters a DetNet domain, it is necessary to add the headers of the DetNet protocol stack. To achieve this, we created the *Push DetNet* action, which is responsible for generating these headers, adding the seqNumber, keeping track of incoming packets, and assigning a FlowId. This functionality is enabled at the ingress Tofino node. Additionally, this node includes the *Replication* action, which creates copies of the original packet and sends them along the possible different paths to the destination, using multicast groups for this purpose.

We highlight also the *Elimination* action. This is enabled at the egress Tofino node, which stores seqNumber of the packets it receives in a register to discard duplicates. Additionally, it maintains a second register that stores the arrival time of the packets. This time is compared against a time threshold. If the arrival time is greater than the threshold, the corresponding entry in the first register is removed. In this way, memory is freed up to prevent it from becoming full.

FIGURE 41: PREOF LOGICAL SCENARIO

8.5.2 Evaluation

Currently, the Replication and Elimination functions implemented in P4 on Tofino switches are operational, and their correct functioning has been verified with 10 Gbps traffic generated using a Spirent traffic generator. The following table shows various amounts of packets sent to the deterministic network along with the corresponding packet losses. In this test, one of the paths was disabled by physically disconnecting a cable to verify that the traffic continues to reach its destination.

TABLE 5: TEST RESULTS ON THE PACKET REPLICATION AND ELIMINATION FUNCTIONALITIES

Id Test	Packets received	Packets transmitted	Packet Losses	Packet Losses (%)	Packets Transmitted (%)
1	49024014	49024014	0	0 %	100 %
2	160445246	160445246	0	0 %	100 %
3	250114384	250114384	0	0 %	100 %
4	59815782	59815782	0	0 %	100 %
5	61533524	61533524	0	0 %	100 %
6	50637574	50637574	0	0 %	100 %
7	40782898	40782898	0	0 %	100 %
8	45984120	45984120	0	0 %	100 %
9	52290030	52290030	0	0 %	100 %
10	57742906	57742906	0	0 %	100 %

Additionally, the sorting function has been developed in DPDK; however, further improvements are required to handle continuous traffic flows effectively.

Both P4 Tofino and DPDK codes are available in the DESIRE6G repository under **PREOF-detnet**. In the **POF-DPDK** subfolder, two Wireshark captures have been included: the first shows 32 unordered DetNet packets, and the second shows the output of the packets after passing through our algorithm developed in DPDK, resulting in 32 ordered packets.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable presents the progress and current state of the unified data plane layer within the DESIRE6G architecture, as developed in WP4 during months 12 to 23 of the project. Building on the initial work outlined in D4.1, this report provides a comprehensive account of the implementation, preliminary evaluations, and plans for the continued refinement of key components.

The document emphasizes the role of these components in enabling the DESIRE6G architecture to meet its goals of programmability, efficiency, and performance. It highlights advancements in site-specific resource management, data plane optimization for unique latency and performance needs, programmable traffic management, and the integration of hardware accelerators.

As an evolving body of work, this deliverable reflects the intermediate progress toward realizing DESIRE6G's unified data plane. The forthcoming public release of updated source code in MS4.3 will further reinforce transparency and accessibility.

10 References

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11 Annex 1

The output manifest of the example NF with its attached network generated by Local NFVO:

```

apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: nf-1
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: nf-1
  template:
    metadata:
      annotations:
        k8s.v1.cni.cncf.io/networks: '[
          { "name": "nf-1-br",
            "mac": "aa:bb:cc:dd:ee:ff",
            "interface": "net1"
          }]'
      labels:
        app: nf-1
    spec:
      nodeName: node1
      containers:
        - name: nf-1
          image: desire6g/nf1:stable
          imagePullPolicy: Never
          lifecycle:
            postStart:
              exec:
                command:
                  - "/bin/sh"
                  - "-c"
                  - |
                    ip addr add 192.168.0.10/24 dev net1
                    ip route add 192.168.1.0/24 dev net1
                    arp -i net1 -s 192.168.1.10 bb:bb:cc:dd:ee:ff
          resources:
            limits:
              hugepages-1Gi: 2Gi
              memory: 2Gi
            volumeMounts:
              - name: dev
                mountPath: /dev
              - mountPath: /hugepages-1Gi
                name: hugepage-1gi
          volumes:
            - name: hugepage-1gi
              emptyDir:
                medium: HugePages-1Gi
            - name: dev
              hostPath:
                path: /dev

```

And the related network attachment definition:

```
apiVersion: "k8s.cni.cncf.io/v1"
kind: NetworkAttachmentDefinition
metadata:
  name: nf-1-br
spec:
  config: '{
    "cniVersion": "0.3.0",
    "plugins": [
      {
        "name": "nf-1-br",
        "type": "bridge",
        "bridge": "nf-1-br",
        "ipam": {}
      }, {
        "capabilities": { "mac": true },
        "type": "tuning"
      }
    ]
  }'
```
